

Ionic liquid-polymer composites: a new platform for multifunctional applications

D.M. Correia^{1,2}, L.C. Fernandes^{2,3}, P.M. Martins^{2,4}, C. García-Astrain³, C.M. Costa^{2,5}, J. Reguera^{3,6}, S. Lanceros-Méndez^{3,6*}*

Dr. D.M. Correia

Centre of Chemistry, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, 5000-801 Vila Real, Portugal

Centre of Physics, University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

L.C. Fernandes

Centre of Physics, University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Dr. P.M. Martins

Centre of Physics, University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

Institute of Science and Innovation for Bio-Sustainability (IB-S), University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

Dr. C. García-Astrain

BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Dr. C.M. Costa

Centre of Physics, University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

Centre of Chemistry, University of Minho, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

Dr. J. Reguera, Prof. S. Lanceros-Méndez

BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48013 Bilbao, Spain

Email: senentxu.lanceros@bcmaterials.net; javier.reguera@bcmaterials.net

Keywords: Ionic liquids, multifunctional materials, polymer composites, smart materials

Ionic liquids (ILs) have emerged as a novel class of chemical compounds for the development of advanced (multi)functional materials with outstanding potential in applications of several areas due to the ILs unique properties and functionalities. The combination of ILs with polymers, in a composite, allows developing smart materials, which synergistically combine the features of specific polymers and ILs. Moreover, ILs can be extensively modified by the

incorporation of functional groups with specific properties into the cation, anion or both. Thus, it is possible to tune the IL, the polymer, or both to obtain a broad spectrum of multifunctional composites and address the specific requirements of many applications.

This work focusses on advanced materials and strategies concerning ILs and polymers for the development of smart IL/polymer-based materials for applications including responsive and sensitive sensors, actuators, environment, batteries, fuel cells, biomedical applications, among others.

1. Introduction

In the past two decades, much attention has been paid to ionic liquids (ILs) due to their new and tunable physicochemical properties ^[1]. The number of publications concerning ILs continually increased in recent years, indicating the considerable attention and potential of these materials (**Figure 1**).

ILs are typically defined as liquid electrolytes composed uniquely by ions and with a melting point below 100 °C (criteria to distinguish molten salts and ILs) ^[2]. They can include a vast number of organic cations and organic or inorganic anions. The first reported IL, the ethylammonium nitrate, was discovered in 1914 by Walden ^[3], being the first generation of ILs reported in the 1970s–80s with the development of the alkyimidazolium halogenoaluminate ILs by mixing aluminum halides with imidazolium halides ^[4].

Figure 1. Number of publications concerning ILs. Source: Scopus (keywords: ILs and composites).

ILs are characterized by their unique profiles based on an interplay between hydrogen bonding, coulombic and van-der-Waals interactions of their ions ^[2a]. These compounds also exhibit a low vapor pressure, usually below the decomposition temperature, and the majority of them are liquid at room temperature ^[5]. Overall, ILs present unique characteristics (**Figure 2**) such as negligible vapor pressure ^[6], high ionic conductivity ($\sim 10^{-3}$ - 10^{-2} S cm⁻¹) ^[7], or viscosities from 2 to 3 orders of magnitude higher than organic solvents ^[8]. Additionally, due to their excellent solubility and miscibility with many compounds (organic, inorganic and polymeric materials) ILs can replace traditional volatile organic solvents in different processes such as organic reactions, catalysis, extraction, and separation, promoting the development of green chemistry and clean technologies ^[1, 4b]. Other advantages are their high thermal stability, usually with a decomposition temperature above 350 °C and excellent chemical and electrochemical stability ^[1, 4a, 6], with an electrochemical window between 4 and 6 V ^[9]. ILs are also considered non-flammable and non-volatile ^[10].

Figure 2. Main physicochemical properties of ILs.

It has been reported the existence of $\sim 10^{18}$ ILs involving the combination of different anions and cations ^[11]. Attending to the cation chemical composition, ILs are commonly classified into three subclasses: aprotic, protic and zwitterionic (**Figure 3**), each one being generally synthesized towards a specific application ^[12].

Figure 3. General classification of ionic liquids with an indication of a representative application area. Adapted from ^[12b].

Aprotic ILs containing large cations such as pyridinium, imidazolium and phosphonium, and smaller anions are the most commonly used. Typical IL anions include inorganic anions (e.g. bromine (Br^-), chloride (Cl^-), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), hexafluorophosphate (PF_6^-), tetrafluoroborate (BF_4^-)) and organic anions such as bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (TFSI), among others ^[13].

Figure 4 represents the chemical composition of the most common cations and anions described in the literature.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the most common cations and anions described in the literature. Adapted from [6].

Protic ILs are prepared by proton transfer through the combination of a Brönsted acid and a Brönsted base, leading to the presence of proton-donor and acceptor sites, which can be used to build up a hydrogen-bonded network [13b, 14]. This kind of ILs has attracted increasing attention for fuel cell applications as new proton conductors and *n*-doped carbon materials using protic ILs as novel small-molecule precursors via direct carbonization treatments instead of traditional polymer precursors, which require more complex procedures and can lead to more impurities on the materials [15].

Zwitterionic ILs results from the addition of ILs to surfactant systems, actuating the ILs as additives with the primary goal of modifying the properties of aqueous zwitterionic surfactants systems. The resulting properties of the system depend both on the type and the extent of the interaction between the cation/anion of the IL with the surfactant head group [6].

The functionalities of the ILs can be tailored through the incorporation of functional groups linked covalently into the cation, anion or both, tuning the ILs properties and increasing their effectiveness towards specific applications such as catalysis, medicine, CO₂ capture, batteries, lubricants, or fuels, among others [1-2, 4a]. The physical properties of ILs can be adjusted

depending on the ionic constituents (alkyl chain length and functional groups) and also the IL properties (magnetic, luminescent and catalytic properties, among others), as well as by their incorporation into other constituents, such as polymers [1]. In this sense, the combination of the ILs functionality with polymers allows the development of smart materials with superior properties when compared with other nanocomposites, increasing the interest and potentiality for several areas of application.

Besides being applied in electrochemistry due to their exciting properties (according to experimental studies, many ILs exhibit high electrochemical stability windows ranging between 4 and 7 V [16]), ILs have emerged as a new trend in materials science. The combination of ILs with specific polymers opens the possibility to develop novel stimuli-responsive materials with different morphologies (films, membranes, fibers and printed), **Figure 5**, with tailored functionality, as a new platform for advanced multifunctional materials, with advantages over traditional smart nanocomposite materials.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the production of IL-based polymer composites for different processing methods.

The main advantage is related to a large variety of ILs, which allows tuning materials responses to a large variety of external environmental stimuli, such as electrical and magnetic fields, heat or light, among others ^[17], based on the vast array of IL functional characteristics ^[18]. The material functionality is a result of the selection of the IL and its properties (e.g. size of cation/anion, viscosity, conductivity, density and molecular weight) and the polymer type. Furthermore, the interplay between the selected IL charges (cations and anions) with the polymer chains, also plays an essential role in the composite properties. As an example, IL with different anions and cations, when incorporated into a poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) matrix will affect the percentage of β -phase (the most electroactive and polar phase) in the composite, and the mechanical properties (acts as a plasticizing agent) ^[19], due to the interaction of the positive CH₂ of PVDF with the negative anion charge and the interaction of the negative holding charge PVDF groups (CF₂ groups) with the IL cation charges ^[19-20]. Another work devoted to evaluating the effect of ILs on PVDF-copolymer morphology indicates that ILs can also induce a porous structure in the polymer matrix ^[21]. Additionally, IL may avoid the need for the addition of more than one filler (active material) to endow a nanocomposite with more than one functionality – altering its original properties negatively.

In **Table 1** it is summarized the ILs functionalities to develop IL-based smart and multifunctional materials.

Table 1. ILs functionalities for the development of smart and multifunctional applications ^[1].

IL-based multifunctional materials	ILs functionality
Responsive and sensitive materials	Photo-responsive pH-sensitive Temperature-sensitive Gas-sensing Ion-responsive Moisture-sensitive Magnetic-responsive Electrochromic ILs with switchable polarity
Optical materials	Luminescent Nonlinear optical Photonic ILs ILs based structural color
Energetic materials	Energetic ILs Hydrogen-storage

The potential applications of such smart/multifunctional materials have been increasing significantly, including nowadays areas such as sensors and actuators ^[20, 22], tissue engineering ^{[23] [24]}, energy generation and storage, such as batteries ^{[25] [26]}, among others (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. IL/polymer-based multifunctional materials application areas.

The focus of this review is to provide the state-of-the-art related to the development of IL/polymer composites for smart and multifunctional applications. There are already rich contributions to this field and a tremendous potential for the development of novel functional responses and applications. In this scope, this manuscript will be only focused on the development of IL/polymer composites with different functionalities and applicability. The functionality of the ILs will be explored in different sections, the first one focusing on smart or responsive/sensitive materials with responsiveness to distinct stimuli, and a second section with (multi)functional materials and their application in different areas.

2. Ionic liquid-based polymer composites and their applications

In this section, the combination of different ILs with polymers for applicability in various fields such as sensors, actuators, batteries and fuel cells, environment and biomedical applications, among others, will be addressed. The main achievements resulted from the IL incorporation into a polymer matrix will be presented. This wide range of applications is intimately linked to the high number of possible combinations of cations and ions from ILs together with a chosen polymer matrix. Moreover, on the one hand, some of the functionalities obtained may result from the intrinsic properties of the IL (e.g. thermochromism). On the other hand, other properties may result from the interaction of IL with polymers (e.g. actuators).

2.1. Responsive and sensitive IL/polymer materials

2.1.1. Photo- and thermoresponsive

The combination of specific ILs with polymers allows the development of smart photo- and thermoresponsive materials, i.e. that exhibit an acute change in the fundamental material

properties by the application of external stimuli, light or temperature variation, for a photo- and thermoresponsive effect respectively. The synergetic combination of polymer and ILs allows higher tunability of the responsiveness and improved mechanical, thermal, electrical or optical properties.

The light stimulus-responsive materials offer a high spatial and temporal resolution, leading to a rapid, non-invasive, and remote control ^[1]. The photo-responsive property of the ILs can be achieved, for instance, through the incorporation of photochromic moieties into either cations or anions. Therefore, changing their physicochemical properties (melting point, conductivity, etc.) upon light irradiation, typically at ultraviolet (UV) and/or visible wavelengths (**Figure 7**) ^[1].

Figure 7. Molecular structure of typical cationic and anionic moieties used for photo-responsive ILs: a: diarylethene, b: stilbene, c: phenylazo-substituted imidazolium, d: azobenzene, e: spiropyran, f and g: cinnamate. Reprinted with permission from ^[1].

Transparent poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)/1-butyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide ([BMPyr][TFSI]) composites were used for the preparation

of solid-state electrolytes for electrochemical devices ^[27]. The incorporation of ILs into PMMA improved the thermal stability and enhanced the luminescence intensity of these IL-based gel-polymer electrolyte membranes. [BMPyr][TFSI] was selected as the IL and produced more amorphous and polar membranes when compared with pure PMMA. These membranes showed good chemical and thermal stability, and the IL increased the conductivity until 20% IL content. The incorporation of IL resulted in high optical transmittance and enhanced luminescence intensity ^[27].

Electrochromic ion gels (also called ionogels, or polymer-based ILs) with the potentiality to alter their optical properties (e.g. absorbance and transmittance) upon the application of an external electrical stimulus for device development have been also gained special attention ^[28]. An electrochromic device (ECD) based on ion gels composed of polystyrene-block-poly(methyl methacrylate)-block-polystyrene, 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([EMIM][TFSI]), an electrochromic (EC) redox molecule (methyl viologen) and an anodic species (ferrocene) were developed. The electrochromic response of the flexible device on plastic occurred upon the application of low voltages (0.7 V). A coloration efficiency of 105 cm²/C and operational stability over 24 h in air demonstrated the strong potential of the device for printed electronics applications (**Figure 8**) ^[28]. Other studies report on the applicability of ILs in the electrochromic devices.

Figure 8. Photographs of the ECDs in the bleached and colored states: before bending (top) and after bending (bottom). The reduction and oxidation process were conducted by applying -0.9 and 0.0 V, respectively. Reprinted with permission from [28].

An ECD based on a mechanically robust, highly ionic conductive gels composed by a random copolymer of poly[styrene-ran-1-(4-vinylbenzyl)-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate] (P[S-r-VBMI][PF₆]) and the ionic liquid [EMIM][TFSI] also demonstrated its active potentiality in electrochemical applications (**Figure 9**) [29]. This flexible ECD on the plastic device showed excellent bending durability against tensile and compressive strains [29]. Other studies report on the applicability of ILs in similar electrochromic devices [30].

Figure 9. a) Molecular structures of components included in the EC gel, b) cyclic voltammogram of the EC gel, in which the dmFc serves as both an anodic species and an internal standard. A Pt electrode, ITO-coated glass, and Ag-wire were used as the working, counter, and quasi-reference electrode, respectively. Voltage dependence of c) UV-vis absorption spectra and d) CIELAB color coordinates ($L^*a^*b^*$) for the ECD, and e) photographs of the ECD at various applied voltages. Reprinted with permission from [29].

Ion gels can also be applied in electrochemiluminescent (ECL) materials. Low-voltage, flexible and ECL polystyrene-block-poly(methyl methacrylate)-block-polystyrene (ABA) triblock copolymers associating into micellar cross-links in the versatile [EMIM][TFSI] containing redox-active luminophores ($\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3\text{Cl}_2$) have been developed for printed electronics [30f, 31] (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10. (a) Schematic of three ECL devices with different luminophore systems: $\text{Ir}(\text{diFppy})_2(\text{bpy})^+$ only, 40 mol % $\text{Ir}(\text{diFppy})_2(\text{bpy})^+$ + 60 mol % $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$, and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ only. (B, c) Photographs of the fabricated three ECL devices (b) as fabricated and (c) in the ON state at $V_{PP} = 4.0$ V and a frequency of 60 Hz. Reprinted with permission from [31].

Similar results were obtained by mixing matrix polymer (P(VDF-HFP)), [EMIM][TFSI], and the same light-emitting transition metal complex ($\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3\text{Cl}_2$) [32].

A photo/thermo-responsive copolymer-based ion gel containing an ABC triblock copolymer with an IL-phobic A block, an IL-philic B block, and an azobenzene-based photo/thermo-responsive C block was studied as photo-responsive soft actuator and photo-healable soft material [33]. While at high temperatures (above the upper critical solution temperature (UPCST)) the system produces micellization of the polymer, at intermediate temperatures the composites exhibited significant rheological changes upon UV or visible irradiation (**Figure 11**). According to the authors, the introduction of an IL-phobic group allowed morphological transition between the jammed micelle structure and the micellar network structure. Thus, this non-volatile and ion-conducting gel offers enormous potential in applications such as light-responsive soft actuators and photohealable soft materials [33].

Figure 11. Variations in the G' and G'' values of 15 wt% ABC(Azo) triblock copolymer in [EMIM][TFSI] by switching UV and visible light irradiation at 60 °C with frequency $\omega = 0.1$ rad s⁻¹ and strain amplitude $\gamma = 1\%$. Reprinted with permission from [33].

The role of the ILs in the actuation behavior of thermoresponsive ion gels was evaluated using poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) as thermo-responsive gels polymerized in the presence of two ionic liquids: ethyl-3-methylimidazolium ethyl sulfate ([EMIM][ESO₄]) or trihexyltetradecylphosphonium dicyanamide ([P66614][DCA])^[34]. It was observed that the ion gel with [EMIM][ESO₄] requires less time to absorb and release water, being excellent for fast response applications. On the other hand, the [P66614][DCA] IL presents a more robust actuator behavior and a significant potential for long-term applications due to its stable response^[34].

Thermoresponsive ionogels based on a random copolymer of P(S-r-BzMA-r-MMA) and ILs ([EMIM][TFSI], 1-ethyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium [PF₆] ([P12][PF₆])) were developed^[35]. The typical thermoresponsive systems are unable to maintain the gel-state at different temperatures. However, the produced thermoresponsive gel maintains a gel-state regardless of the environment temperature^[35].

Another type of thermoresponsive materials, thermochromic ones, can be obtained with ILs containing transition metals. Thermochromic materials can contribute, among others, to enhance the energy efficiency of buildings and vehicles, leading to a reduction in energy consumption and CO₂ emission. The incorporation of thermochromic ILs into a transparent/translucent solid matrix is in the genesis of a new generation of thermochromic materials. Thus, solar-thermochromic devices have been developed using thermochromic IL/PVDF composites [36]. The incorporation of 1-(3-hydroxypropyl)-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([C₃OHMIM][BF₄]) in the presence of [BMIM]₂[NiCl₄] (1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium nickel tetrachloride) or [Ni(Me₄en)(acac)][ClO₄] (Me₄en = N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine; acac = acetylacetonate) in a PVDF porous matrix results in two different thermochromic responses as presented in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12. Visible spectra and color images (insets) of the thermochromic properties of composite IL/PVDF films with: a) film of C₂OHmimBF₄[BMIM]₂[NiCl₄]/PVDF and b) C₃OHmimBF₄[Ni(Me₄en)(acac)][ClO₄]/PVDF with a mass ratio of 5:1:10. Reprinted with permission from [37].

Films containing [BMIM]₂NiCl₄ show a rapid color transition from transparent (for films with a thickness below 0.05 mm) or translucent (for films thicker than 0.10 mm) to royal blue by

heating from room temperature to ~ 70 °C (**Figure 12a**). On the other hand, films containing $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_4\text{en})(\text{acac})]\text{ClO}_4$ show a slower transition from grass-green at room temperature to light yellow-green at ~ 40 - 50 °C and coffee red at temperatures >70 °C (**Figure 12b**). In both cases, the color transitions were reversible, and a concomitant electrical conductivity increase was produced upon increasing the temperature.

The thermochromic properties of the $[\text{BMIM}]_2[\text{NiCl}_4]/\text{PVDF}$ films also revealed a potentiality to be applied as printable sensors^[38]. The capacity of these materials to change from transparent to a dark blue color has been attributed to the tetrahedral complex NiCl_4^{2-} , after a dehydration process. (**Figure 13**). As a result of the dehydration process that takes place, decreasing the number of ions into the matrix leading to a conductivity decrease. Hence, the high potential of these materials for thermosensitive and thermochromic printable sensors in different areas such as temperature sensors, water level sensors (**Figure 13e**), smart windows, among others^[38].

Figure 13. a) Current vs voltage curves, (b) electrical conductivity of the PVDF/IL composites as a function of [BMIM]₂[NiCl₄] content, (c) Cyclic temperature dependence of the DC electrical conductivity between 30 and 150 °C for the composite containing 40 % wt. of [BMIM]₂[NiCl₄] and (d) Resistance variation with the temperature. e) PVDF based [BMIM]₂[NiCl₄] hot water level sensor based on PVDF/[BMIM]₂[NiCl₄] composite containing 40 % wt. of IL. Reprinted with permission from [38].

As mentioned above, one of the more prominent applications of thermo-chromic IL/polymer-based materials is in smart windows. IL/polymer-based materials can also be employed in smart windows. Aiming at this application, ionogels based on polyurethane (PU) with different

imidazolium ILs (namely 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [BMIM][TFSI] and 1-butyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [BDMIM][TFSI], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [EMIM][TFSI] and 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [HMIM][TFSI]) were developed for smart windows [39]. They were tested for over 5000 heating-cooling cycles switching from opaque to highly transparent (**Figure 14**), without losing their thermal, and optical stability. The ionogels showed high transparency ($T_{lum} = 87\%$) and luminous modulation ($\Delta T_{lum} = 80\%$) below and above the transition temperature (LCST). The composites with better results concerning the transition temperature were the ones containing the ILs [BDMIM][TFSI] and [BMIM][TFSI]. Furthermore, the incorporation of plasmonic nanoparticles into the ionogels endowed thermochromic ionogels with dual responsivity to temperature increase and to high-intensity irradiation [39].

Figure 14. a) Transmittance spectra of flexible ion gels containing 33% wt. [BDMIM][TFSI] and 67% wt. [BMIM][TFSI] at different temperatures with the insets showing the transparent, translucent, and opaque states. b) Optical performance reversibility of the ion gel containing 35% [BDMIM][TFSI] and 65% wt. [BMIM][TFSI] during 5000 cycles, each cycle represents

transparent and opaque states containing heating, holding, cooling, and holding steps. Reprinted with permission from [39].

Ionogels thermoelectric materials combining the polymer PVDF-HFP and three distinct ILs ([EMIM][TFSI], 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([BMIM][BF₄]) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide ([EMIM][DCA]) were developed [40]. These materials have shown a remarkable Seebeck coefficient (up to 26.1 mV K⁻¹), high ionic conductivity (6.7 mS cm⁻¹), low thermal conductivity (0.176 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) and high thermoelectric properties as a result of the ion-dipole interaction between the polymer and ILs [40]. These ionogels reveal a suitable property towards the conversion of the intermittent heat into electricity and are remarkable to harvest the low-grade thermal energy on earth. Similarly, other ionogels have been synthesized to be applied for future thermoelectric applications [41].

2.1.2. pH-sensitive materials

Few studies report the combination of polymers and ILs for the development of pH-sensitive materials. A flexible pH sensor membrane was developed through the combination of poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) with Quinhydrone (QH) and the IL n-cetylpyridinium hexafluorophosphate (CPFPP) [42]. The CPFPP-PVC-QH flexible and stable membrane highly improves the performance QH-based sensors presenting a fast response time (smaller than 10 s), higher potentiometric response with pH-sensitivity between 2 and 9.5, stability and reproducibility (**Figure 15**).

Figure 15. a) Dynamic response of the CFP-PVC-QH membranes with increasing pH in the solution in 0.5 pH steps. b) Reproducibility of the membrane electrode in the buffer solution with pH 4 and 7. Reprinted from [42].

2.1.3. Magneto-sensitive materials

The incorporation of magnetic ILs into a polymer matrix allows producing a new type of magneto-responsive materials. Magneto-ionic composites based on poly(vinylidene trifluoroethylene) P(VDF-TrFE) and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrachloroferrate ([BMIM][FeCl₄]) films were presented as suitable low-field magnetic sensing devices [43]. The IL/P(VDF-TrFE) composites revealed a high magneto-ionic output with a α_{ME} magnetolectric coefficient of $10 \text{ V cm}^{-1} \text{ Oe}^{-1}$ (**Figure 16**), proving their applicability as magneto-sensing device as well as their applicability in printing technologies [43].

Figure 16. Magnetic response of [BMIM][FeCl₄]/(PVDF-TrFE) composites. a) Magnetization of the [BMIM][FeCl₄]/(PVDF-TrFE) composite films at room temperature from -600 Oe to 600 Oe. b) Extrapolation of the magnetization of the [BMIM][FeCl₄]/(PVDF-TrFE) composite films at room temperature and 2 Oe magnetic field intensity as a function of the magnetic ionic liquid content. Reprinted with permission from ^[43].

2.1.4. Piezoresistive sensors

Acrylate polymers have been used in combination with ILs for the fabrication of stretchable piezoresistive tactile sensors. The performance of 2- [[(butylamino)carbonyl] oxy] ethyl acrylate (BACOE) containing [EMIM][BF₄] was evaluated as sensors ^[44]. BACOE is a commercially available 3D printing material, which can be polymerized by a photo-initiated free radical polymerization mechanism. The performance of the piezoresistive sensor was tuned by the crosslinking density and molecular weight of the matrix, which governs the mobility of the polymer chains and IL domains ^[44]. The cross-linking and polymerization were controlled by adjusting the amount of cross-linking agent and UV exposure time, respectively, which in turn affects the sensitivity of the sensors. It was shown that the piezoresistive properties depend on the rearrangement of polymer chains and IL domains inside the composite produced by the deformation of the material. When the compressive strain increases, the distance between two electrodes decreases and the motion of the chains and IL occurs, decreasing the electrical resistance of the materials ^[44]. The 3D printability of polymer/[EMIM][BF₄] piezoresistive pressure sensors was also reported. For the assembly of the sensor, an intermediate layer of polymer/IL composite was placed in between two carbon nanotube-based electrodes ^[45]. The screen-printed sensor was then embedded on the inner surface of a 3D printed tire to provide pressure data at contact points between the tire and the road. The developed sensors provided

information about different parameters such as road conditions and monitored the tire structural health and movement, among others ^[44].

2.1.5. Bio and humidity sensors

Few studies report on the development of IL-based polymer materials for biosensors. For the detection of biomolecules such as dopamine (DA), ascorbic acid (AA) and uric acid (UA), composite electrodes based on the conducting polymer PEDOT and [BMIM][Cl] IL were produced ^[46]. To create the electrochemical sensors, PEDOT was first electropolymerized in a screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE). Subsequently, the [BMIM][Cl] was spin-coated onto the surface. The final electrode showed peak potentials of 0.06, 0.23 and 0.35 V and detection limits of 1.15, 0.39 and 0.27 μM for AA, DA and UA respectively with excellent linearity, resolution, and sensitivity ^[46].

The combination of polymers and ILs was also studied for the development of humidity sensors based on two different ILs, methyl 3-(3-(2-hydroxyethyl)imidazole-1-yl)propanoate chloride salt (IL-Cl), methyl 3-(3-(2 hydroxyethyl)imidazole-1-yl)propanoate bromate salt (IL-Br) ^[47]. The IL-PEG electrolyte, with a molar ratio of 4:1 of IL-Br to IL-Cl, were synthesized through an ester-exchange reaction and later these IL-PEG composites were mixed with polyurethane (PU) and poly-1,4-butylene adipate glycol (PBA) forming PU/PBA/IL-PEG composites with different IL-PEG contents. The IL-PEG acted as an antistatic agent under low relative humidity (RH) with the surface resistivity of the composites changing very slightly at different RH percentages (**Figure 17a**). These results also showed that the synthesized composites could be used as antistatic materials ^[47].

Figure 17. a) Relative humidity effect on the surface resistivity of different IL/polymer composites at room temperature. Reprinted with permission from [47]. b) The sensitivity of the [Bmim][FeCl₄]/PVDF composites comprising different IL contents (5, 10 and 20 %wt.) to humidity. Reprinted with permission from [22c].

Humidity sensitive materials based on [Bmim][FeCl₄]/PVDF composites comprising different IL contents were also developed [22c]. The performance of the composites as humidity sensing was evaluated through the variation of the humidity between 35-90%. The authors observed a linear resistance variation with the relative humidity as is observed in **Figure 17b**, decreasing the resistance of the materials with the IL content increase due to higher mobility and number of the IL ionic charges [22c].

2.1.6. Electromechanical actuators

IL/polymer composites have been successfully used for the development of low voltage and large deformation electroactive actuators. The actuators are formed by an ionic polymer composite and two conductive and flexible electrodes at each side. When an electrical field is

applied, there is an ion diffusion within the polymer matrix and therefore a bending response is produced as a consequence of the cations and anions movement, and its distribution near to the electrodes (**Figure 18**)^[20]. These electroactive actuators are stable over repeated bending cycling and can operate in a wide temperature range due to the thermal stability of ILs^[48].

Figure 18. Schematic representation of the ion migration and bending response. Reprinted with permission from^[20].

Among the different electroactive polymers, PVDF is known for its high dielectric constant, polarity and ionic conductivity^[49]. Thus, actuators based on PVDF and ILs with different anions, [HMIM][Cl] and HMIM][TFSI] have been developed to study the effect of anion size and filler content on the bending response^[50]. It was observed that the polymer crystallizes in the electroactive β -phase in the presence of the ILs, regardless of the nature and content of the IL. Moreover, the size of the polymer spherulites decreases with increasing IL concentration and with the incorporation of anions of larger size (**Figure 19**).

Figure 19. SEM images of pristine PVDF (a); IL/PVDF composites with [Cl] anion with different IL contents: 25% (b) and 40% (c) and for composites with the [TFSI] anion with 40% (d) IL content. Reprinted with permission from ^[50].

The electrical conductivity of the material depends on the amount of IL and the anion size, whereas the bending is related to the degree of crystallinity, mechanical properties, and ionic conductivity. The best bending values were obtained for 40 wt% [HMIM][Cl] content ^[50].

Different imidazolium-based ILs were also incorporated into a PVDF matrix to study the effect of the alkyl chain length of the cation ([EMIM]⁺, [HMIM]⁺ and [C₁₀MIM]⁺), and the anion ([TFSI]⁻ and [Cl]⁻) on the mechanical and electrical properties of the composites ^[50]. The mechanical properties are nearly independent of the IL type, whereas the conductivity is more related to the anion type than to the size of the alkyl chain. The maximum bending response (0.3%) was obtained for the IL [EMIM][TFSI] (**Figure 20**) ^[50]. The effect of film thickness on the properties of PVDF/[EMIM][TFSI] was also assessed, and it was observed that the bending actuation of the composites varies inversely with the sample thickness ^[22b].

Figure 20. Picture of the bending motion comparing two different ILs (a) [HMIM][Cl]/PVDF and (b) [EMIM][TFSI]/PVDF under an applied voltage of 10 and 20 V square signal, respectively at a frequency of 0.1 Hz. Reprinted with permission from ^[50].

The influence of cation type comprising ILs sharing the same anion ([TFSI]⁻) and different cations in the actuator performance was also evaluated. The bending measurements showed a displacement increase with the cation chain length increase. Further, it is also dependent on the conformation of the cation size, being the highest bending response observed for the PVDF/[PMIM][TFSI] (5.7 mm) and PVDF/[PMPPIP][TFSI] (6.0 mm) (where PMIM and PMPPIP represent 1-propyl-3-imidazolium and 1-methyl-1-propylpiperidinium), composites at 100 mHz ^[20] (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21. Displacement of the composites for an applied voltage of 5 V and a frequency of 100 mHz (a) and as a function of frequency (b). Reprinted with permission from [20].

The influence of the polymer matrix into the actuator performance has also been evaluated with the IL [EMIM][TFSI] within different fluorinated matrixes [22a], showing that the actuator performance depends on the polymer type, the most substantial bending response being obtained for the IL/PVDF-TrFE composites with 40 wt% of IL (~3.5 mm using a frequency of 100 MHz at an applied potential of 5.0 V_{pp}) [22a].

PVDF was also used in combination with N,N,N-trimethyl-N-(2-hydroxyethyl) ammonium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([N_{1112OH}][TFSI]) and [EMIM][ESO₄] in order to study the cation effect [22b]. Similarly, to previous results, the crystal phase of PVDF was independent of the IL type, whereas the degree of crystallinity and the electrical conductivity depended on the IL type and content. Composites with a 40 wt% of [N_{1112OH}][TFSI] showed the highest electrical conductivity and the best strain bending response was obtained when using 25 wt% of the same IL. The results revealed that the bending response is more dependent on the IL content than on its type. Moreover, composites with [EMIM][ESO₄] are not cytotoxic opening the way to a wide range of actuator applications in the biomedical field [22b].

Electromechanical actuators can also be obtained through the IL uptake by a preformed polymeric membrane. The electromechanical performance as a function of the temperature of

Nafion membranes containing [EMIM][Tfo] and gold nanoparticles as anionic materials [51] lead to actuators with lower cationic curvature with increasing temperature and the deformation rate was slow with increasing temperature up to 50 °C. On the other hand, a higher anionic curvature with increasing temperature was observed, and the rate of deformation was increased at 60 °C (Figure 22).

Figure 22. a) Schematic representation of cationic and anionic bending mechanism and sequential overlaid images of the cationic and anionic bending. b) Graphs of the maximum cationic curvature and cationic actuation time at different temperatures, respectively. Reprinted with permission from [51].

This behavior was explained by changes in the IL structure, such as dispersion of ion clusters in the IL and the number of drifted ions. However, a loss of functionality was observed above 60 °C that was due to a change in a break of some Nafion inner structures and nano-channels. The current flow increases up to 80 °C, and an abrupt increase was observed at 90 °C [51].

The actuation mechanism of dry-type polymer actuators composed of single-walled carbon nanotubes, an IL, and a base polymer (named as nanocarbon polymer (NCP)), in a three layers configuration, was also evaluated [52]. In the same way as the previous case, the NCP actuators showed a bending motion toward the anode at low times and even a reverse movement over time (back-relaxation) in the lower frequency ranges of the applied DC voltage. In this case, the amount of backward motion and time response could be modified by changing the amount of IL in both the electrolyte and in the electrode layers [52].

High-performance polymer printable actuators comprising the [EMIM][TFSI] IL, a soluble sulfonated polyimide (SPI), and carbon materials with an ionic conductivity up to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ were developed [53]. The actuators exhibited large displacements and a wide potential window of up to 3.5 V. The displacement of the printable actuators was proportional to the accumulated electric charge in the electrodes and independent of the carbon materials [53].

Conductive elastomers were prepared to combine Imidazolium-based ILs with epoxidized natural rubber (ENR). This material presents interesting properties towards sensor and actuator applications. Natural rubber is a renewable material with properties such as elasticity and excellent mechanical properties [54]. However, its heat resistance and electrical conductivity are low and, thus, several attempts have been carried out to improve the electrical conductivity using polar derivatives of natural rubber such as ENR. Moreover, the preparation of ENR/ILs composites could further enhance the conductivity of the rubber. After the addition of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride [EMIM][Cl] IL up to a specific concentration, an increase in the vulcanization rate was observed, decreasing curing time. The electrical conductivity of these

rubbers increased to 10^{-6} and 10^{-4} S m⁻¹ with 3 and 10 parts of IL per hundred rubber, respectively, and the DC conductivity also increased with IL content. The mechanical properties were also affected by the incorporation of ILs due to reported plasticizing effect retarding the strain-induced crystallization of the rubber and the cross-linking degree varied as a function of the concentration of IL [54].

Transparent actuators made of poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethane sulfonate ([EMIM][CF₃SO₃]) were prepared by spray casting of the electrodes. PDMS shows excellent properties such as elasticity, transparency, versatile surface chemistry, low water permeability and low electrical conductivity, becoming an interesting candidate for the preparation of sensing and energy-conversion devices. The potential of the as-prepared materials as actuator stems from the electrostatic double-layer capacitor and Faradaic capacitor mechanisms [55].

Naturally derived IL/polymer actuators have also been developed. Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB)/ 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([BMIM][TFSI]) soft actuators water and moisture resistant with a reversible macroscopic bending for applied potentials from 0.1 to 7 V and an excellent operation durability up to 105 cycles at 2 V were developed [56]. These actuators demonstrated to be still responsive at low voltages. They showed a maximum tip displacement of 0.2 mm ($\epsilon = 24.4 \times 10^{-6}$) at 0.1 V, increasing the actuation with the applied voltage ($\epsilon = 1430 \times 10^{-6}$, at 7 V). Besides the displacement increased at lower frequencies, the authors reported that the frequency values down to 0.1 Hz were lower than the maximum amplitude achievable applying a DC voltage [56].

2.2. Functional IL/polymer materials applicability

2.2.1. Environmental applications

During the last decades, the huge population growth and industrialization have created tremendous environmental problems. The anthropogenic activities produce contaminants such as dyes, metal ions, and other organic and inorganic chemicals that are hardly removed from water^[57]. As these chemicals are potentially toxic to humans and animals^[58], it is mandatory to remove them before discharge into water bodies or release into the air. Many techniques have been employed on environmental remediation, but adsorption presents many attractive advantages as high selectivity and efficiency, sludge free process, remarkable reusability, easy operation, environmentally friendly and cheapness^[59]. Additionally, the adsorption process may be applied to the two most contaminated environments in nature – air and water^[60]. The unique properties of ILs allow designing (changing cations and anions) specific modified adsorbent materials, with specific physical-chemical properties, that match the specificity of a pollutant^[59].

The combination of sorbent materials and IL can produce enhanced results in the scope of environmental remediation. In addition to those properties, IL can be a greener alternative to the classical toxic solvents used during materials production, reducing the pollution generated in the industry^[61]. The following subchapters will address these materials both in air and in water.

Air remediation

Among some environmental problems, global warming and high energy consumption have attracted considerable interest over gas separation, especially about the CO₂ continuous increase^[62]. In this way, several works report on gas-sensing and gas-separation composites based on polymers and ILs. In this context, imidazolium-based ILs have been used in gas separation applications taking advantage of their high CO₂ solubility, diffusivity, and permeability^[63]. Their permeation selectivity is larger than ammonium-based and phosphonium-based ILs. The acidic hydrogen in the cation affects CO₂ solubility via hydrogen bonds^[63-64]. Anions such as

PF₆, BF₄, and TFSI, provide higher solubility in CO₂ compounds due to the presence of fluorinated groups. Further, CO₂ acts as a Lewis acid and the anion as a Lewis base, and the CO₂ solubility is attributed to the proximity of the CO₂ and the anion ^[65].

To achieve efficient and economic separation of CO₂ Pebax (poly(amide-b-ethylene oxide)) has shown to be a good gas separation material, being Pebax 1657 one of the most attractive commercial Pebax due to its CO₂ high separation performance. The transport properties for Pebax 1657 revealed the highest solubility selectivity for CO₂/H₂ when compared with other Pebax compositions due to the polar components present in both soft and hard segments ^[66]. A research team ^[63] developed three different composites containing Pebax 1657 (poly(amide-b-ethylene oxide)), zeolite imidazolate framework nanoparticles, and different imidazolium-based ILs. The effect of the anion presents in the IL and the nanoparticle content over the gas permeability and selectivity of the membranes was evaluated by using ILs based on [BMIM] cation with different anions of [TFSI], dicyanamide [DCA] and [BF₄]. The results confirm that the anion plays an essential part in CO₂ permeability (**Figure 23**), moreover, [BMIM][TFSI] seems to act as a low molecular weight additive resulting in a more amorphous structure and higher fractional free volume of the membranes. The incorporation of IL also enhances the compatibility of nanoparticles with the polymeric matrix, leading to higher CO₂/N₂ selectivity. In short, the results indicate that the permeability of the as-prepared membranes was up to 4.3 times higher than for pristine Pebax.

Figure 23. CO₂ gas permeability of Pebax/IL membranes as a function of IL content for ILs with different anions. Reprinted with permission from [63].

Estahbanati et al. [64] also studied the incorporation of [BMIM][BF₄] into Pebax 1657 membranes and its effect over gas permeation at 35 °C and 2-10 bar, showing that the addition of the IL to the membrane decreases its crystallinity, which results in an increase in permeability for the tested gases. Moreover, CO₂ permeability and selectivity are enhanced with increasing IL, the permeability becoming up to 70% higher than for neat Pebax membranes. The selectivity for CO₂ concerning CH₄ and N₂ was 17% and 34% higher, respectively [64].

How the composite is generated, the processing also plays a substantial role in the performance of this composite in CO₂ separation. The effect of incorporation of [EMIM] [BF₄] into Pebax 1657 in the form of Pebax-based hollow-fiber gel membranes (**Figure 24**) [67] showed that after the addition of IL, a 300% improvement in CO₂ permeability was observed. It was shown that the IL interacts with ethylene oxide segments via hydrogen bonding, leading to a decrease of the polymer crystallinity, inhibiting the potential interaction with CO₂ and, thus, lowering the gas permeability below the estimated value using homogeneous blend model. Even though, the as-prepared membranes showed high mechanical durability, chemical stability and good CO₂

separation for mixed-gas feed with permeance up to 300 GPU and CO₂/N₂ and CH₄/N₂ selectivities of 36 and 15, respectively [67].

Figure 24. SEM image of the cross-sections of hollow fiber Pebax/IL gel membrane (a); Effect of feed pressure on CO₂ permeance for neat Pebax®1657(●), Pebax®1657/IL20%(■), Pebax®1657/IL40%(▲), Pebax®1657/IL60%(▼), and Pebax®1657/IL80%(◆). Reprinted with permission from [67].

Ion gels were prepared using a sulfonated polyimide (SPI) and different hydrophobic ILs, namely, [BMIM][TFSI] or 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ([BMIM][PF₆]) for the fabrication of gas separation membranes. The incorporation of ILs leads to softer membranes, due to the plasticizing effect of the IL and an increase of the gas permeability. Thus, [BMIM][TFSI] containing composites showed CO₂ permeability of 412 Barrer against the 0.58 Barrer in the pure SPI, and selectivity against N₂. The [BMIM][PF₆] containing SPI composite show lower permeability but improved separation coefficient ($\alpha = P_{CO_2} / P_{N_2}$) – ranging between 33 to 37 [68].

To overcome the drawbacks of many porous polymer membranes for the separation of industrial gas mixtures such as reduced mechanical and thermal stability at elevated temperatures, poly(pyromellitimide-co-4,4'-oxydianiline) (PMDA-ODAPI) and polybenzimidazole (PBI) were used in combination with ILs for the preparation of composite

membranes. The polymers were selected due to their high thermal stability and durability as well as for their ability to form dense membranes ^[3]. PBI is a fully aromatic heterocyclic polymer with high thermal stability and excellent chemical resistance ^[69], whereas PMDA-ODAPI is a polyimide also known as “*Kapton*” that also shows high thermal stability, mechanical strength, and solvent resistance. The incorporation of [BMIM][TFSI] with a low melting point and good stability increased the CO₂ permeation without decreasing the selectivity and, thus, the composites are promising for CO₂ separation ^[70].

Polysulfone (PSF), a thermoplastic polymer with excellent mechanical, thermal, chemical and film-forming properties have been widely used for the preparation of membranes, also with the incorporation of imidazolium-based ILs [EMIM][TFSI] and 1-ethyl-3-methyl imidazolium trifluoromethane sulfonate ([EMIM][CF₃SO₃]) for CO₂/methane separation ^[71]. Results indicated that CO₂ solubility in ILs is determined by factors such as operating pressure, temperature, nature of the anion and the anion chain ^[71]. Also, the presence of fluorine chains and halide ions seems to improve CO₂ solubility ^[72], and thus, higher CO₂ solubility is expected for [EMIM][TFSI] due to its fluoromethyl chain and lower viscosity. The CO₂ permeation increases after the addition of ILs, whereas the methane permeation significantly decreases. In fact, [EMIM][TFSI] containing membranes show higher CO₂ permeation values, whereas membranes containing [EMIM][CF₃SO₃] result in better CO₂/CH₄ selectivity values. Consequently, these kinds of membranes are ideal for CO₂/CH₄ separation. The use PSF membranes for CO₂ separation ^[73] has also been based on the incorporation of triethanolamine formate (TEAF) and triethanolamine acetate (TEAA), being observed that the CO₂ permeability increases with the addition of ILs and the highest performance were observed 20-30 wt% ILs content ^[73].

Further, a composite porous membrane based on PEO, the IL [BMIM][BF₄], and different loadings of CrO₃ nanoparticles were used for CO₂/N₂ separation ^[74]. With increasing CrO₃ content, the solubility in CO₂ increases with the generation of chromate esters while no

permeance of N₂ was observed (**Figure 25**). The composites were also tested in a gas mixture showing a maximum selectivity of the membranes for a mole ratio of CrO₃ of 0.1 wt%.

Figure 25. Performance of the PEO/BMIM-BF₄/CrO₃ composite membrane: a) single-gas permeance and b) CO₂/N₂ selectivity in a gas mixture. Reprinted with permission from [74].

New nanocomposites containing ILs have also been explored for the preparation of gas separation membranes. Poly(urethane) (PU) foams from castor oil as polyol have been prepared with different ILs, including [BMIM][Cl], [BMIM][BF₄] and 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-3-methyl imidazolium glycinate ([EOHMIM][Gly]) [75]. The composites prepared using higher IL content showed high density and small pore sizes. The higher capacity capture (425 mg CO₂ g⁻¹ at 25 bar and 25 °C) was observed when using 15% of [BMIM][Cl] IL. At higher IL contents, the capture ability decreases probably due to the pore size. On the other hand, CO₂/CH₄ selectivity increases with increasing IL content [75].

Another important environmental problem is the removal of particulate matter from the air, to address this issue, the vinyl polymers have been used to prepare filters. For instance, poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) (PPy) and poly(acrylamide) (PAM) were mixed with lanthanide ILs (1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium hexanitratolanthanate ([C₈mim]₃La(NO₃)₆) and 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium pentanitratoeuropate ([C₈mim]₂[Eu(NO₃)₅]) showing particulate adsorption higher than 99% (**Figure 26**) [58]. This efficiency was maintained above 90% for 15 h, and the filters can be reused after regeneration (removal of the adsorbed particulate matter).

The luminescent properties of lanthanides from IL allow monitoring of the adsorption process (change of fluorescence intensity).

Figure 26. The photos of La-10PVP film a) before and b) after the long-time adsorption experiment. SEM images of La-10 polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) c) before and d) after regeneration, and the reuse experiment curves of e) particulate matter (PM) 2.5 and f) PM10.

Adapted and reprinted with permission from [76].

Nafion-ionic liquid-SiO₂ superhydrophobic nanocomposite membranes using tetramethylammonium hydroxide ([TMA][OH]) IL have been used for water vapor separation. The composite membrane proved to be an alternative for water vapor separation from flue gas with a permeance up to 2131 GPU and H₂O/N₂ selectivity of 130 [77].

Water remediation

Alongside with air, water pollution is among the most worrying environmental problems of the last decades [57]. To address this problem, many new materials have been developed, and IL are among the materials used for environmental remediation applications, especially related to contaminants adsorption and photocatalysis.

Nowadays, not many works use IL for environmental applications. However, there are already some works devoting attention to IL-based materials for these applications [61]. Works like the one developed by Guifen *et al.* [78], show the high potential of IL towards environmental remediation. The authors produced a novel IL-polymer composite (IL-P) by attaching 1-butyl-3-vinyl imidazolium bromide ([BVIM][Br]) into a vinyl-functionalized silica surface. The adsorption tests were performed against two different aromatic compounds, 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP), bisphenol A (BPA), 2,4-dinitrophenol (2,4-DNP), 2-isonaphthol (2-NP) using pristine silica, vinyl-silica, and the IL-P (**Figure 27**). The results show that IL-P sample adsorbed the highest amount (239.7, 68.39, 56.86 and 64.28 mg g⁻¹, respectively) in the shortest time (15-60 min) (Figure 1). The authors attribute the notable results to the presence of IL on the silica surface, where π - π and ionic interactions may occur between the positively charged imidazolium ring (IL) and the negative charged aromatic ring from phenolic contaminants. Moreover, the IL-P proved good reusability properties after solvent treatment.

Figure 27. Adsorption kinetics curves of 2,4-dichlorophenol (a), bisphenol A (b), 2,4-dinitrophenol (c) and 2-isonaphthol (d), on silica (circle), vinyl silica (square) and IL-P (triangle) at 25°C (black curve), 35°C (red curve) and 45°C (blue curve). Experimental conditions: pH 7.0, m sorbent = 10 mg, V_{solution} = 10 mL. Reprinted with permission from [78].

Another sorbent material was developed by Huawei and colleagues to remove anionic dyes from water [79]. The magnetic core coated with silica was functionalized with poly(ionic liquid) (PIL), using the IL monomer (dimethyl-dodecyl-4-vinyl benzyl ammonium chloride (DMDVAC), to obtain a Fe₃O₄@SiO₂@PIL nanocomposite (**Figure 28**). These materials were tested in the removal of solutions containing alizarin red (AR), thionin acetate (TA), malachite green (MG) and acid orange II (AO), or mixtures of these dyes.

Figure 18 - Synthetic route to Fe₃O₄@SiO₂@PIL MNPs. Reprinted with permission from [79].

The results indicate that the Fe₃O₄@SiO₂@PIL completely removed AR from the solution. However, TA removal was significantly lower ($\approx 14\%$), indicating that besides highly efficient, the nanocomposite presents remarkable selectivity (**Figure 29a**). Similarly, to the previous work, the authors attribute the AR sorption efficiency to the π - π interactions, hydrogen bonds, and electrostatic interaction. On the contrary, electrostatic repulsion occurs between cationic dyes (i.e. MG) and PIL inhibiting the dye adsorption and enhancing the selectivity. This is shown in **Figure 29b**, after mixing MG and AR into one solution. Fe₃O₄@SiO₂@PIL can adsorb and remove selectively AR from the solution, after magnetic separation, leaving only MG in the treated solution.

Figure 29 - Adsorption behavior to solo and mixed dyes. (a) The removal rate of AR and TA by different adsorbents at an initial dye concentration of $50 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, adsorption selectivity of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@\text{SiO}_2@\text{PIL}$ to (b) MG/AR at an initial dye concentration of $20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Reprinted with permission from [79].

An interesting magnetic sorbent material was developed using cellulose- Fe_3O_4 as a core-shell structure functionalized with polymeric ionic liquid (PIL) generated using epichlorohydrin and 1-methylimidazole (**Figure 30**). The adsorbent was tested against the Congo red (anionic dye)[80].

Figure 30 - Schematic representation of the production of Fe_3O_4 @cellulose nanohybrid, with a novel polymeric ionic liquid (PIL). Adapted and reprinted with permission from [80].

To understand the parameters that affect Congo red adsorption onto the Fe_3O_4 @cellulose nanohybrid, the authors performed several tests, which indicate that adsorption is more dependent on contact time, adsorbent dosage, and ionic strength. The best results show that Congo red adsorption reached the equilibrium after 11 min and maximum uptake of 131 mg g^{-1} . The authors stated that the interaction between the dye and the methylene groups from the adsorbent surface explains the sorption of dye. Moreover, π - π interactions between the imidazolium ring and the dye can lead to π - π bonds between both. After three cycles, the magnetic sorbent also revealed remarkable reusability (still in the range between 90-95%), proving the suitability for water remediation applications.

Another natural polymer-based material was developed, reporting on a new hybrid material combining chitosan and ionic liquids (CS-IL) (**Figure 31a**) for anions adsorption ($\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and PF_6^-)^[81].

Figure 31 - a) SEM image of spherical nanoparticles (diameter \approx 250 nm). b) Sorption of PF_6^- as a function of the time for CS-IL conjugation at (a) pH = 3.00 and (b) pH = 7.00 - original chitosan at pH 3.00 (c) and 7.00 (d), respectively. Reprinted with permission from ^[81].

The results depicted in **Figure 31b**, indicate that the CS-IL composite has a higher ability to adsorb PF_6^- . The maximum adsorption capacity ($0.840 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$) was obtained after 90 minutes of contact time for CS-IL conjugation (Figure 23b – trace a). The CS-IL sorbent was also efficient on the adsorption of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, with a maximum adsorption capacity of $0.422 \text{ mmol g}^{-1}$. The authors attribute this improvement to ionic liquids, as they enhance the solubility of the composite. Additionally, the results also indicate that the higher the degree of amino substitution (DS) of chitosan, the larger the adsorption rate. It is essential to highlight that CS-IL material not only dissolves better in solution, when compared with pristine chitosan but also it aggregates in water after sorption facilitating the separation process, which can be a remarkable property for real upscale applications^[81].

IL-Hydrogels also represent new materials towards the sorption of cationic or anionic pollutants. The work reported by ^[82], presents the production of Poly(AM-co-[Amim]Cl-co-DADMAC)

hydrogel (PAMDA) by water solution copolymerization with imidazole-containing ionic liquid 1-allyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([AMIM][Cl]), Dimethyldiallylammonium chloride (DADMAC) and acrylamide (AM) as monomers (**Figure 32a**).

Figure 32 - a) FE-SEM images of PAMDA with 5 wt% [AMIM][Cl]. b) Effect of contact time on the adsorption capacity of PAMDA at various temperatures (initial Cr(VI) concentration: 100 mg L^{-1} ; adsorbent dosage: 0.1 g ; $\text{pH} = 2$). Reprinted with permission from [82].

This work indicates that the adsorption equilibrium for Cr(VI) was reached in only 10 minutes (**Figure 32b**), for all the tested temperatures. According to the authors, the maximum adsorption capacity of Cr(VI) of 74.5 mg L^{-1} was achieved at 323 K (Langmuir isotherms). The incorporation of IL was critical to achieving such results, as IL enhanced the wettability of the composite and also increased the ionic conductivity by the introduction of the positively charged [AMIM][Cl].

Similarly, to remove Cr(VI), a new functional material based on ionic liquid-based cross-linked polymer, polydivinylbenzene (PDVB) - 1-aminoethyl-3-vinylimidazolium chloride hydrochloride IL (PDVB-IL), was produced (**Figure 33**) [83].

Figure 33 - Influence of pH on the adsorption capacity of PDVB-IL towards Cr(VI) (initial concentration = 0.1 g L^{-1} , $T = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, contact time = 30 min, PDVB-IL = 0.1 g L^{-1}) (a); Adsorbed amount of Cr(VI) by PDVB-IL as a function of contact time at different initial concentrations of Cr(VI). ($T = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, PDVB-IL = 0.1 g/L). Reprinted with permission from [83].

Several parameters were evaluated on the adsorption of Cr(VI), and the results indicate that the maximum sorbent capacity increases with the decrease of the pH value 12 to 2 (Figure 25a). Additionally, the adsorption kinetics assays show that chromium ions are adsorbed rapidly during the first 5 minutes (Figure 25b). Afterward, the adsorption reached the equilibrium, which reflects a large number of adsorption sites available on the PDVB-IL surface. The maximum adsorption capacity, after 5 minutes at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, was 391.4 mg/g . The IL plays a decisive role in the adsorption process as the ammonium groups from the adsorbent surface promotes the attraction with HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ forms of Cr(VI).

These first works show the enormous potential of ILs for environmental applications. However, more studies need to be performed concerning the development of IL/polymer-based composites for air and water remediation. Additionally, it is also crucial to start testing the specificity between pollutants and sorbent materials and address real water bodies remediation applications.

2.2.2. Energy applications

2.2.2.1. Batteries

Ionic liquids (ILs) are intensively investigated for energy storage applications in batteries. Their unique properties solve some of the common safety problems ^[7] caused by liquid electrolytes (typically composed by a lithium salt in a mixture of one or more solvents ^[84]), which are: short circuits, often leading to overheating and ignition, causing the battery explosion ^[85].

ILs for battery applications are mostly formed by a quaternary ammonium cation (e.g., aliphatic quaternary ammonium, imidazolium, pyrrolidinium, and piperidinium) and an inorganic/organic anion as are summarized in **Figure 34. Table 2** shows the commonly used ILs in the batteries field. Typically, they have significantly higher viscosities (typically, 30–50 cP) and lower ionic conductivity (RTILs: $0.1\text{--}5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) compared to commercially liquid electrolyte solution ($8.2\text{--}11.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and 0.5–4 cP) ^[86]. The factors controlling the diffusion of ions in ILs are the size of ion, the shape of ion, the magnitude of the interaction between cation and anion, the conformational flexibility, the molecular mass of the ion, and the effects of nanostructures in ionic liquids ^[87]. The diffusion of ions becomes fast for ILs with low viscosity and high ionic conductivity ^[87]. Furthermore, higher electrolyte viscosity imposes significant rate capability limitations for all but the most fluid IL electrolytes ^[88].

Figure 34. Common ILs used for energy applications. Reprinted with permission from [89].

ILs have high applicability in different areas of battery cells. They are used in the synthesis of the electrodes [90], in the electrode slurry preparation [91], in solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) [92], as electrolyte additive [93] and in polymer composite as solid polymer electrolyte [94] [95]. In addition to battery systems, these polymer/IL composites can be used for supercapacitor, in which good compatibilization between IL and polymer matrix is essential to obtain a high ionic conductivity value and excellent mechanical properties [96].

Table 2 – Cation/anion used in battery applications ^[97].

Cation	Anion
EMIM	Cl, BF ₄ , TFSI, BETI, MSI, OTf, TA, FSI, FSA, TFSA, PF ₆ , DCA
BMIM	BF ₄ , TFSI, PF ₆ , TA
C ₈ MIM	TFSI
C ₁₀ MIM	TFSI
MDI	BF ₄ , TA, TFSI, PF ₆
M1,2E31	TFSI
DMPI	TFSI, Me
P13	MSI, FSI, TFSI, PF ₆ , FSA
P14	TFSI, MSI

Ion Gel

Recently, thermotropic ionic liquid crystalline lithium salt, lithium bis (1,3-dibutyl-4,5-imidazoledicarboxylate tetrafluoroborate) borate (LiBIB), with potential bilayer fast ion conductive tunnels, having functionalities of both lithium salt and polymer host or electrolyte, was synthesized and showed better ionic conductivity ($3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) and electrochemical stability at room temperature in comparison with those of traditional lithium salts ^[98]. Novel ILs have been also functionalized with ether oxygens to suppress crystallization and with bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (FSI) anions to improve ionic conductivity. Cell batteries with these ILs were assembled and showed a nominal capacity of 150 mAh g^{-1} at C/10 (1C was 1.08 mA cm^{-2}) while retaining flat potential profiles throughout 50 cycles ^[99].

ILs are an important element in solid electrolyte interphases (SEI) where it has been observed that the interaction of an IL adlayer with lithiated graphite leads to a stable passivation layer, which inhibits the deintercalation of Li ^[92]. For SEI-layer based on IL, different cation

chemistries and kinds of structural modifications were tested, with the introduction of nitrile groups and double bonds giving rise to a SEI layer protection and a fast Li⁺ transport ^[100].

Ion gel membranes have become excellent substitutes of the liquid electrolytes for a wide range of applications such as batteries, fuel cells, supercapacitors, or energy units, among others. Solid-state electrolytes offer certain advantages when compared with their liquid homologues addressing some of their problems such as liquid leakage, gas formation due to solvent decomposition or thermal lack of stability. In this sense, ion gel electrolyte membranes are receiving increasing attention due to their thin-film-forming capacity, transparency, flexibility, high ionic conductivity and wide electrochemical window ^[101]. In particular, IL electrolytes have a wide range of conductivities and thermal stability, becoming a potential substitute for liquid electrolytes. The polymerization of suitable vinyl monomers in the presence of ILs generates ion gels with good ionic conductivities, transparency, and flexibility. These materials fulfill the requirements for the design of polymer electrolytes for solid-state electrochemical devices.

For these Polymer/IL composites, several polymer matrixes have been proposed: poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) ^[102], poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) ^[103] and its copolymers (poly(vinylidene fluoride-trifluoroethylene, PVDF-TrFE and poly(vinylidene fluoride-hexafluoropropylene, PVDF-HFP) ^[104] among other ^[105], and with several combinations of IL.

The effect of the incorporation of poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) containing IL on the properties of PVDF membranes was investigated ^[106] showing that the interaction of imidazolium cation and CF₂ groups with PVDF lead to nonpolar α -phase into polar β and γ phases transformation. Moreover, PEG interactions with PVDF can favor the amorphous regions of PVDF decreasing its crystallinity. Higher values of dielectric permittivity were observed, and the incorporation of IL together with thermal annealing improved de conductivity. Additional annealing increased the ion mobility by chain motion and polar phase crystals ^[106].

Further, PVDF derivatives also show high anodic stability due to the presence of strong electron-withdrawing functional groups [26b]. PVDF copolymers have been reported as the best polymer for the design of gel polymer electrolyte systems due to its semi-crystalline structure that displays good compatibility along with its mechanical strength. As for PVDF and PVDF-HFP polymer, the incorporation of ILs influences the microstructure, thermal stability and ionic conductivity of the polymer.

PVDF has been also blended with PVA for the preparation of gel polymer electrolytes for lithium-ion batteries. After the incorporation of IL (N-methyl-N-butyl-piperidine-bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (PP₁₄)), the membranes showed high ionic conductivity of $1.19 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and the presence of IL resulted in improved electrochemical stability and higher discharge capacity [107]. The cathode delivered a discharge capacity of $104.6 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ and a Coulombic efficiency over 95% after 99 cycles. Moreover, it was observed a good electrolyte wettability that improves ion transfer between electrodes [107].

The effect of different amounts of IL on the nucleation and electrical transport properties of PVDF-HFP membranes was evaluated [108], showing that the use of N, N-diethyl-N-(2-methacryloylethyl)-N-methylammonium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide ([DEMM][TFSI]) decreases the crystal growth and enhances electroactive β -phase transformation. The maximum ionic conductivity was $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for the highest IL content. The authors observed that even if the ionic conductivity and segmental motion are coupled when using low IL content, increasing the amount of IL resulted in a decoupling of both phenomena.

Solid polymer electrolyte

Solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) consists of an ionic liquid dissolved in a polymeric matrix placed between the electrodes and is essential because lithium mobility must be high enough to prevent significant mass transfer limitations to the charge and discharge processes [109]. In the case of the solid polymer electrolyte, the mechanism of conduction is by both hopping of the

Li^+ ions and the segmental motion of the polymer chain, the rate of which is related to the T_g of the polymer [110]. Moreover, the aggregation of IL moieties into percolating nano-domains within the polymer matrix could be used as an approach to decouple the ion/polymer dynamics [111].

SPE based poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) PHEMA and lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide [BMIM][TFSI] was prepared by solvent casting technique in which the addition of salt and ionic liquid in the PHEMA matrix, it helps in increasing the ionic conductivity of the polymer electrolyte from $2.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for PHEMA + 30 wt% LiPF_6 to $8.01 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ with the addition of 50 wt% [BMIM][TFSI] [112].

SPE based on Poly(vinylidene fluoride-trifluoroethylene) (PVDF-TrFE) and $[\text{N}_{1112}\text{OH}][\text{TFSI}]$ IL were investigated in which it was observed that the ionic conductivity increases with IL content increasing, showing a maximum value of $1.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for a 32 wt% of IL (**Figure 35**) [113].

Figure 35. Cross-section SEM images of the P(VDF-TrFE) membranes with different IL contents: a) 0 wt%, b) 4 wt%, c) 16 wt% and d) 32 wt% and e) ionic conductivity for different IL contents. Reprinted with permission from [113]

PVDF-HFP is one of the most used polymers in SPE. It has been doped with several IL such as, 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([EMIM][BF₄])^[107], 3-methyl-1-propylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide ([PMIM][TFSI])^[114], 1-methyl-3-propylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([P13][TFSI])^[26b], propyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([PMMI][TFSI])^[26b], 1-methyl-3-propylpiperidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([PP13][TFSI])^[26b], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([EMIM][TFSI])^[115] and ionic liquids based on trifluoroacetate anion and different alkylammonium (diethyl-, dimethylethyl-, tributyl-, diisopropylethyl-) cations^[116].

The polymer/IL composite PVDF-HFP/([EMIM][BF₄]) experimented an increase in polymer amorphicity after the addition of the IL and [Li][BF₄] salt^[107]. This change in crystallinity was concomitant with an increase of ionic conductivity up to 15 wt% of IL with a conductivity of $0.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and a transference number (defined as the ratio of the conductivity of ions to the total conductivity) of 0.98^[107].

Other composites based on PVDF-HFP have also shown good conductivities. For instance, PVDF-HFP/([PMIM][TFSI]) revealed high conductivity values of $1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, good interfacial stability and high discharge capacities with 96% retention after 50 cycles^[114]. The hydrophilic or hydrophobic nature of ILs, [EMIM][BF₄] and [EMIM][triflate] and hydrophobic [BMIM][PF₆], respectively, were evaluated after incorporation to PVDF-HFP membranes. Ionic conductivities higher than $10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 100 °C were recorded, and the materials were incorporated into electrochemical cells, using graphite electrodes^[117].

1-methyl-3-propylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([P13][TFSI]) has been reported to be compatible with Li metal and, thus, to be very useful for its use in rechargeable lithium batteries. This IL possesses a wide electrochemical stability window and low viscosity^[26b]. Thus, this IL was used for the preparation of stable, elastic, flexible, and non-volatile polymer gel electrolytes using PVDF-HFP and [Li][TFSI]. The performance of [P13][TFSI]

was compared with other ILs, namely, [EMIM][TFSI], and 1-propyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([PMMI][TFSI]). The composites showed high electrochemical stability and high ionic conductivity. Moreover, the addition of small amounts of ethylene carbonate improved the ionic conductivity as well as the Li-ion transport [26b].

Hydrophobic IL/polymer composites electrolytes have also been synthesized and tested in lithium-air batteries [118]. The electrolytes were composed of ([PMMI][TFSI]), PVDF-HFP and silica. The ionic conductivity of the electrolyte was $1.83 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. In ambient atmosphere tests the compact structure, interface resistance obtained by the Nyquist plot in the Li/composite electrolyte/Li cell is stable after 10 days, as seen in **Figure 36**, and reasonable cyclability were observed meaning that the polymer composite electrolyte might provide an opportunity for the fabrication of rechargeable lithium-air battery for practical application (**Figure 36**).

Figure 36. AC impedance plots (Nyquist plots) of cells with different electrolytes at various times: (a) Li/composite electrolyte/Li cell; (b) Lithium air cell by using pure [Li][TFSI]-[PMMI][TFSI] as an electrolyte and (c) Lithium air cell by utilizing [Li][TFSI]-[PMMI][TFSI]-silica-PVDF-HFP polymer composite as the electrolyte. Reprinted with permission from [118].

PVDF-HFP membranes in combination with active ceramic $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Al}_x\text{Ge}_{2-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LAGP) and ILs ([EMIM][TFSI]) were also explored for lithium batteries [119]. High ionic conductivity

values were recorded, and good compatibility with the lithium electrode was observed. Moreover, the electrolyte suppressed the growth of lithium dendrites, showing good interface stability^[119].

The use of PVDF-HFP for rechargeable magnesium batteries has also been investigated by the preparation of PVDF-HFP gel polymer electrolytes using a magnesium salt or magnesium triflate in [EMIM][Tfo]^[120]. The resulting materials were semi-transparent and flexible and showed good mechanical strength. Moreover, the conductivity of the material was $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, which shows excellent stability, and the Mg^{2+} ion transport number was 0.26, an appropriate value for magnesium batteries^[120].

Apart from the well-studied PVDF-HFP, PEG derivatives are being investigated as adequate polymers for the fabrication of electrolytes in battery applications due to its advantages such as high flexibility, electrochemical stability, and affinity to lithium ions. To increase the ionic conductivity of PEG, ILs have been incorporated into these types of networks. [EMIM][TFSI] was incorporated into PEG-based polymers with lithium salt-containing also [Li][TFSI] as gel electrolytes for lithium-ion batteries^[121]. The flexible films were prepared by curing a mixture of poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether and lithium 3-glycidyloxypropanesulfonate or lithium 3-(glycidyloxypropanesulfonyl)(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide with poly(ethylene glycol) bis(3-aminopropyl) terminated. Conductivity values of $1.16\text{-}2.09 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ were recorded for these samples without [Li][TFSI] and $0.29\text{-}0.43 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for those incorporating 10 wt% [Li][TFSI].

PEG polymer with N-n-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide ([Pyr14][TFSI]) IL have been also studied. In this case, electrospun silica nanofibers were added as reinforcing additive, and [Li][TFSI] was used as the Li salt. The presence of IL improved the conductivity over $10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 80 °C. The electrolyte was tested using galvanostatic cycling of a prototype Li/LiFePO₄ polymer cell and a specific capacity of about 150-160 mAhg⁻¹ was recorded^[122].

BMIM and EMIM were used in combination with PEG and silica nanoparticles for the preparation of composite polymer electrolytes. The molecular weight of PEG influenced the structure and the conductivity of the composites. Smaller PEG chains increased the conductivity, but higher molecular weight PEGs were needed to maintain the integrity of the material. The highest room temperature conductivity obtained was $1.24 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for an IL content of 55 wt% [123].

The incorporation of different room temperature ILs into PEG/lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate (LiTf) composite electrolytes prepared by melt compounding and containing sepiolite modified with D- α -tocopherol PEG succinate as filler was evaluated [124]. The room temperature ILs can form solid electrolyte interphase that avoids the formation of Li dendrites in Li batteries. The conductivity was increased as a function of the temperature and lithium diffusion (D_{Li}) while maintaining the mechanical and rheological properties of the composites, as is shown in **Figure 37** [124].

Figure 37. (a) Conductivity (σ) as a function of T as obtained from the conductivity experiments (the inset presents the high-temperature range in linear scale), (b) Lithium diffusion (DLi as a function of the viscosity (η) of the liquid phase employed to prepare the electrolyte, RTIL or EC. S20 is included as a green circle, (c) FTIR in the $\nu(\text{SO}_3)$ region of Tf illustrating the solubility of LiTf in the medium, and (d) σ as a function of (DLi+ DTf) at 25 °C for M series electrolytes. Reprinted with permission from [124].

A new SPE based on polysiloxane with grafting ionic liquid and poly(ethylene oxide) (PEG) chains onto flexible polysiloxane backbone was produced presenting high ionic conductivity ($3.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature), excellent resistance to dendrite growth and excellent cycling performance for Li/LiFePO₄ as is shown **Figure 38** [125].

Figure 38 - The performance of Li/SPE3/LFP cells at 30 °C: (a) charge/discharge capacity and coulombic efficiency at 0.1 C rate, (b) discharge/charge profiles at 0.1 C over a potential range of 2.5-4.2 V for selected cycles. Reprinted with permission from [125].

Flexible PEG/([Li][TFSI]) SPE assisted with a bifunctional ionic liquid (IL) of tetrabutylphosphonium 2-hydroxypyridine (TBPHP) as well as a garnet-type fast ion conducting ceramic of Li_{6.4}La₃Zr_{1.4}Ta_{0.6}O₁₂ (LLZTO) was produced. PEG8-[Li][TFSI]-TBPHP-12.5% LLZTO showed ionic conductivity of $9.39 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, a wide electrochemical window of

more than 5.0 V, a high transference number (t_{Li^+}) of 0.63 at 50 °C and the battery exhibited excellent rate performance ^[126].

Polyimides are also interesting polymers for the design of gel polymer electrolytes due to their good electrochemical stability and affinity for electrolyte solutions. The electrochemical performance of $LiMn_{0.4}Fe_{0.6}PO_4$ as a cathode for lithium batteries was tested in an electrospun polyimide film containing [Li][TFSI] in [BMIM][TFSI] ^[127]. These composites showed good mechanical strength and thermal stability and initial discharge capacities of 163.6, 136.6, and 121.6 mAhg⁻¹ at 0.1, 1, and 2 C-rate current densities, respectively. The stable performance of the cell resulted from the low impedance resistance of the electrolyte/electrode pair ^[127].

Renewable polymers have also been used in combination with ILs to make cleaner and more environmentally friendly materials for energy storage applications such as batteries.

Cellulose derivatives also found many applications in the preparation of SPE for biodegradable energy storage devices such as methylcellulose ^[128]. Hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose (HPMC) has been reported to favor ion adsorption on the polymer ^[129]. Due to the hydrophobic character of HPMC and low conductivity, HPMC combined with [BMIM][Tfo] allows improving its ionic conductivity ^[130]. The addition of ILs decreased the degree of crystallinity of the electrolyte while enhancing the ionic conductivity up to $2.36 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, indicating that the incorporation of IL enhances polymer chain mobility and favors the conduction of ions ^[130].

Hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) was used to prepared SPE for batteries and supercapacitors using fumed silica nanoparticles, magnesium trifluoromethanesulfonate salt and [EMIM][Tfo] as IL. Electric double-layer capacitors were fabricated using activated carbon electrodes, and a specific capacitance of 25.0 F g⁻¹ was obtained. Moreover, around 70% of its capacitance was maintained after 1600 cycles ^[131]. To tackle the main drawbacks of the supercapacitors (drying and narrow electrochemical range), a new ion gel-based in Li⁺ and hydroquinone (HQ) containing ionogel (PVDF-co-HFP + [EMIM][TFSI]) were produced. The results indicate that an optimal HQ concentration, the device possesses a higher transmittance contrast (~91 %),

high coloration efficiency ($\sim 61.9 \text{ cm}^2/\text{C}$), high areal capacitance ($\sim 13.6 \text{ mF}/\text{cm}^2$), and good charging/discharging cyclic stability (**Figure 39**)^[132].

Figure 39. (a) Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) profiles at $0.4 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ within a potential range of 0 to -1.5 V and corresponding in-situ transmittance change measured at 700 nm . Photographs of the device at eight points designated in (a) during (b) charging and (c) discharging. Reprinted with permission from^[132].

The use of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) for the fabrication of SPEs has also been reported by preparing a lithium metal polymer battery with low charge-transfer resistance using PLA and $[\text{Pyr}_{14}][\text{TFSI}]$.^[133] The prepared SPEs are thermally and electrochemically stable and were tested with lithium iron phosphate and carboxymethyl cellulose-based cathodes showing promising cycling performance. The coulombic efficiency at a current of 0.015 mAcm^{-1} was higher than 99% in most cycles^[133].

The effect of the IL type on the phase-separation of poly(acrylonitrile-*r*-butadiene) (PAN-*r*-PB), was studied to the preparation of gel-like electrolytes^[134]. The composites were prepared using CN-modified silica nanoparticles to increase their compatibility with acrylonitrile, Li triflate and six different ILs ([BMIM][BF₄], [BMIM][TfO], [EMIM][TfO], 1-butyl-4-methylpyridinium tetrafluoroborate ([4MBP][BF₄]), and 1-butyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([BMMIM][BF₄]). ILs containing hexyl or octyl substituents at the imidazolium rings produced higher mobility of PB-rich phases and decrease the PAN-rich phase content, improving the Li-ion conductivity. Even if the PB-rich phase does not take part in Li-ion conductance, after the incorporation of IL, it becomes more mobile, and the PAN-rich phase is also more disordered, increasing the conductivity^[134]. On the contrary, when decyl to dodecyl substituents was used, the hydrophobic tails of PB-rich phase were ordered, and that produced stiffening of the phase, decreasing the conductivity. This strategy allows for the tuning of the properties of the composites by using different ILs and, thus, the prepared materials are promising for Li-ion batteries^[134].

PVA has been widely used for the preparation of gel polymer electrolytes due to its functional properties such as nontoxicity, good film-forming ability and low cost^[135]. However, these gels show low ionic conductivity and the addition of ILs could improve their performance as supercapacitors.

Hyperbranched star polymers with hyperbranched polystyrene as core and polymethylmethacrylate block poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate as arms have been used for the preparation of polymer electrolyte membranes using ILs such as [BMIM][BF₄] or [BMIM][PF₆] and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide ([Li][TFSI])^[3]. Multi-arm star polymers result interesting for polymer electrolyte design due to its structure that restricts the crystallization of polymer and favors charge carrier's migration. Membranes with excellent flexibility and transparency were obtained with conductivities of 2.5×10^{-4} and 4.1×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹ for composites with 40% of [BMIM][BF₄] and [BMIM][PF₆], respectively.

The composite containing [BMIM][PF₆] showed better performance with good thermal stability, wide electrochemical window, excellent interfacial compatibility with lithium electrode and reversible cyclability ^[3] (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Impedance spectra. a) HBPS-(PMMA-b-PPEGMA)30/[BMIM][BF₄]/ [Li][TFSI] with 30 wt% [BMIM][BF₄]. b) HBPS-(PMMA-b-PPEGMA)30/[BMIM][PF₆]/[Li][TFSI] with 30 wt% [BMIM][PF₆] received on a Li/polymer electrolyte/Li symmetric cell at room temperature. Reprinted with permission from ^[3].

Solid polymer electrolytes based on poly(ethylene glycol) monomethyl ether acrylate and [EMIM][Tfo] and [EMIM][TFSI] ILs were developed for capacitor applications ^[136]. It was found that the capacitance increased with the IL content and was influenced by the size of the ion.

[BMI][BF₄] could fill the ionic clusters of poly(ether ether ketone) (SPEEK) driven by electrostatic attractions forming interconnected channels. These channels generated easier pathways, due to acid-base pairs along the surface of SPEEK produced by IL and enhanced the conductivity of the membrane. A conductivity of $9.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, 52 times higher -than the neat SPEEK membrane when using 43% IL was observed ^[137]. Moreover, the electrostatic interactions prevented IL leaching under anhydrous conditions ^[137].

1-butyl-3-methyl-imidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ([BMIM][Tfo]) has also been used in combination with SPEEK membranes and ethylene glycol as cross-linker. The ethylene glycol was used as cross-linker to prevent the leaching of the IL and enhance the mechanical properties of the membrane. The conductivity of the as-prepared membranes between 30 and 140 °C was in the range of 10^{-3} S cm⁻¹, increasing with temperature and IL content ^[138].

ILs have also been incorporated to SPEEK membranes in combination with inorganic fillers such as zeolite or silica. A common problem faced in solid-state membranes is the loss of IL due to the water generated in the cathode and the enhancement of IL fluidity and membrane motility at elevated temperatures that favor IL leaching. Inorganic fillers can form hydrogen bonds between IL and the polymer and improve retention of IL as well as network mechanical properties. The influence of different ILs [BMIM][BF₄], 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ([BMIM][Tfo]), [BMIM][Cl], diethylmethylammonium trifluoromethane-sulfonate ([DEMA][Tfo]) and [EIM][Tfo] on the properties of SPEEK membranes containing silica was evaluated ^[139]. The leaching was decreased after the incorporation of SiO₂, and both anions and cations seemed to play a role in the proton conductivity. Among the different composites prepared, those containing [BMIM][BF₄] showed the highest proton conductivity (15×10^{-3} S.cm⁻¹) under anhydrous conditions as this IL has moderate electrostatic interactions ^[139]. In the case of [DEMA][Tfo], the thermal stability of the composites has shown a clear improvement when compared with neat SPEEK membranes. The sulfonic group seemed to prevent IL leaching, and the presence of silica could further reduce the loss of IL and increases the mechanical properties of the membrane. The reported proton conductivity for these membranes was 2×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ using 50 wt% of IL ^[140]. Zirconium oxide has also been used as a filler to improve the retention of IL. SPEEK-based membranes using diethylmethylamine triflate ([DEMA][TfoH]) and zirconium oxide present excellent mechanical, thermal and chemical stability. The use of 6 wt% of zirconia increased the conductivity due to the formation of the fractal structure of connected aggregates. Moreover,

as reported, the interaction of IL with these aggregates forms new channels and favors conductivity ^[141].

Polymeric ionic liquid

In addition to the SPE composites for battery systems, the polymeric ionic liquid (PIL) has been intensively studied in which they are synthesized from monomers of IL. Several ionic liquids are used for the polymerization, including: triethylmethylammonium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (N₁₂₂₂FSI) ^[142], EMImTFSI or PYR14-TFSI (EMIm: 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium, and PYR14: 1-butyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium) ^[143], 1-vinyl-3-dodecylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (VDIM-TFSI) ^[144], *N*-Propyl-*N*methylpyrrolidinium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (C3mpyrFSI) ^[145], 1-vinyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ^[56] and 1-butyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bis(fluoromethane sulfonyl) (BuMePyr-TFSI) ^[146].

2.2.3. Fuel cells

Fuel cell technologies, which convert chemical energy directly into electrical energy, are one of the promising alternatives for energy storage, due to their relatively high efficiency and environmental compatibility. Fuel cells with polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) can present advantages such as high power density, quick start-up, lower cost, and long life span ^[147]. The formation of composites with ILs can enhance their properties and can contribute to the implantation of these technologies.

PVDF-HFP membranes incorporating 2,3-dimethyl-1-octylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonylimide ([DMOIM][TFSI]) have been developed and tested in a commercial fuel cell test station at 100 °C with hydrogen and oxygen as gas reactants. The membrane showed a conductivity of $2.74 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 130 °C, and it was electroactive for

hydrogen oxidation and oxygen reduction, showing good properties towards proton exchange membrane fuel cell application ^[148]. The same authors reported conductivity values of $0.96 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for PVDF-HFP/[DMOIM][TFSI] composites after the addition of triflic acid that increases the conductivity by providing free H^+ ions. These membranes were thermally stable up to $200\text{-}300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and were electroactive for hydrogen oxidation and oxygen reduction ^[149].

Anion exchange membranes were prepared using quaternized chitosan, a linear polysaccharide derived from chitin found in the shells of crustaceans, cross-linked with glutaraldehyde and a synthesized gemini-type basic morpholine ionic liquid ([Nbmd][OH]) with strong alkalinity and good solubility ^[150]. The increase of IL content improved the thermal stability of the composites as well as the OH^- conductivity ($1.37 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-2}$). The methanol permeability was also assessed and resulted in being $2.21 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature ^[150]. This value is lower than that reported for Nafion, turning these composites into good candidates for methanol fuel cells, which could be used as portable power sources ^[150].

Poly(phenylene ether) (PPO) was combined with a series of ILs to produce proton exchange membrane fuel cells. Different ILs with methyl, ethyl and hydroxyethyl groups were employed to investigate the effect of the structure on the ion conductivity. The use of ILs increased the ionic conductivity, being the highest value 2.5 times higher than that of the neat polymer. In this case, TiO_2 nanoparticles were also incorporated to increase the ionic conductivity further and prevent IL loss. The results show that the swelling ratio was low, and the thermal stability and mechanical properties fulfill the requirements for fuel cell applications. The best results were obtained when using TiO_2 nanoparticles and ethyl-based IL. These membranes showed conductivity values of $59.27 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, and a degradation rate of ionic conductivity near 28% under strong alkali conditions ^[151].

ILs have also been incorporated into vinyl polymers for the development of composites for different applications, such as fuel cells. The polymerization of vinyl monomers in the presence

of ILs resulted in transparent, mechanically robust and highly conductive polymer composites [152]. Styrene, acrylonitrile, divinylbenzene, and benzoin isobutyl ether were polymerized in the presence of 1-vinyl-3-butylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)-imide ([VBIM][TFSI]). The IL acted as a hydrophobic phase, and the composites showed excellent thermal and mechanical stability as well as high proton conductivity ($10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) at high temperatures (180 °C) (**Figure 41**). The resulting membranes are good candidates for proton exchange for fuel cells application, particularly at high temperatures due to the aforementioned properties [152].

Figure 41. a) Proton conductivity of [VBIM][TFSI]_x-VIM_y at different x-y ratios. NTF₂ is the same as TFSI. Reprinted with permission from [152]. b) IL retention rate of Nafion/[DEMA][Tfo]/MHSi membranes measured at 25 °C and relative humidity of 50%. N-IL: Nafion/140 wt% IL; N-IL-4S: Nafion/140 wt% IL/4 wt% MHSi; N-IL-8S: Nafion/140 wt% IL/8 wt% MHSi; N-IL-12S: Nafion/140 wt% IL/12 wt% MHSi [153].

Nafion/[DEMA][Tfo] composites for proton exchange membrane doped with mesoporous hollow silica spheres (MHSi) were applied for fuel cells [153]. Both the MHSi and the protic IL were used to lower the dependency on the water content of the proton conductivity within the membrane, with the latter being responsible for an anhydrous proton conductivity. The effect of MHSi content, 4, 8 and 12 wt% in the composite membranes was studied with a retention rate in the final higher than 50% when MHSi was used, in comparison to the 32% IL retention

in the membranes without MHSi, **Figure 41b**. The best results were obtained for the membranes with 12 wt% of MHSi with an anhydrous proton conductivity of $14.7 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [153].

Hydroxyl functionalized imidazolium ionic liquid $[\text{C}_3\text{OHMIM}][\text{BF}_4]$, IL-OH and $[\text{BMIM}][\text{BF}_4]$ have been developed to prepare intermediate temperature PEM fuel cells where IL-OH can act both as proton acceptor and donor [154]. The incorporation of SiO_2 nanoparticles into the Nafion membranes was also investigated. The combination of the IL and SiO_2 enhances the hydrogen-bonding interactions in Nafion membranes with high anhydrous proton conductivity values at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (**Figure 42**). Moreover, hydroxyl functionalized ILs are more compatible with the electrode reactions in $\text{H}_2\text{-O}_2$ fuel cells [154].

Figure 42. Temperature-dependent anhydrous ionic conductivities of the recast Nafion, the Nafion/IL-OH(50)/ $\text{SiO}_2(10)$ and the Nafion/[BMIM][BF_4] (50)/ $\text{SiO}_2(10)$. Reprinted with permission from [154].

The properties of Nafion membranes make them particularly appropriate for the development of PEM fuel cells. This material is particularly interesting for fuel cell applications due to its stability under cell electrolysis and oxidizing environments [155]. The aggregation of sulfonic acid groups results in the formation of ionic domains that allow the proton conductivity. The

hydration of the membrane determines the proton conductivity and water evaporation results in a collapse of these ionic domains. Thus, some drawbacks such as low conductivity over 100 °C and low relative humidity when using water as a solvent still should be faced. Some PEM fuel cell applications require higher temperatures and constant conductivity, such as in the automobile industry.

Moreover, the efficiency of PEM fuel cells increases at higher temperatures since less pure hydrogen feeds are used. To circumvent these drawbacks, graphene oxide (GO) and 2,3 dimethyl-1-butyl imidazolium dihydrogen phosphate ([DMBUIM][H₂PO₄]) were incorporated into Nafion membranes ^[156]. GO imparts thermal stability and hydrophilicity to the membrane while ILs allow proton transport. In this way, the water retention capacity increased, and proton conduction is ensured regardless of the water content. ILs containing dihydrogen phosphate anions are particularly interesting for PEM fuel cell applications due to their high viscosity, high thermal stability up to 200 °C, high ionic conductivity and suitable proton carrier ^[156].

Hyflon-ion membranes have a similar chemical structure to Nafion with a shorter side chain and their interactions with ILs have also been studied using hydrophobic 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide ([BMIM][BTI]). Mistry et al. ^[157] studied the uptake of [BMI][BTI] within Nafion and Hyflon membranes. The conductivity increased with increasing temperature up to 160 °C using ILs, and the proton conductivity was two orders of magnitude higher than for conventional Nafion membranes. Nylon membranes are also promising since even if the proton conductivity was reduced due to the short side chains, they showed higher thermal stability ^[157].

The effect of six different ILs over the mechanical properties, thermal stability, ion exchange capacity and conductivity of Nafion membranes were evaluated ^[155]. Several imidazolium (HMIM, BMIM, and BMPyr) based ILs bearing hydrophobic tris(pentafluoroethyl)trifluorophosphate (FAP), bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (BTSI), PF₆, and the more hydrophilic BF₄ anions were used in this study. The anion type influenced the

uptake and absorption time of the ILs, whereas the hydrophilicity of the IL was responsible for the washing out of the IL from the membranes. The ion exchange capacity of the membranes was evaluated, and it was found that IL cations partially replaced the protons in Nafion membranes. ILs changed the mechanical properties, acting as plasticizers, and reducing the elastic modulus of the materials. Moreover, conductivity values of $1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were reached, 100 times higher when compared with unimpregnated membranes and the best results were obtained when using HMIM with the bulky and hydrophobic anion FAP^[155].

As it has been mentioned before, Nafion membranes have been widely used for the preparation of solid-state membranes for fuel cell applications. However, Nafion membranes possess some limitations, such as elevated cost and poor stability at high temperatures. To overcome these drawbacks, the use of SPEEK or sulfonated poly(ether ketone) (SPEK) membranes have been explored. These low-cost membranes show notable thermal and chemical stability and, thus, are suitable candidates for fuel cells operating at elevated temperatures^[158]. Moreover, SPEEK membranes with optimized sulfonation degree display higher conductivity than Nafion^[159].

The incorporation of impregnated [BMIM][BF₄] into SPEEK membranes for fuel cells was investigated^[158]. After the impregnation with IL during 2 min, the thermal stability of SPEEK membranes was increased (**Figure 43**) and presented higher conductivity values of $1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The power density in the membrane electrode assembly was 0.13 W cm^{-2} , and the current density was 0.54 A cm^{-2} . These results indicate that the IL interacted with the sulfonic acid groups of the polymer via ion-exchange processes. However, when the impregnation time of IL increased (15min), the conductivity decreased. This counterintuitive behavior was attributed to the exchange of protons in the sulfonic acid groups with BMIM cations. The cations could block the movement of the protons and show non-conductive nature^[158].

Figure 43. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curves of (a) PEEK; (b) [BMIM][BF₄] (same than [BMI.BF₄]); (c) SPEEK; (d) SPEEEK/ BMIM⁺, 2-min contact time and (e) SPEEEK/BMI⁺, 90-min contact time in a 0.1 mol L⁻¹ [BMI][BF₄]. Reprinted with permission from [158].

The incorporation of zeolites and IL into SPEEK membranes was studied using [BMIM][CF₃SO₃] or 1-decyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ([C₁₀MIM][CF₃SO₃]) ILs [159]. The presence of zeolite and ILs improve the water uptake, thermal stability, and proton conductivity. The proton conductivity of the membranes was $3.34 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and $5.98 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for composites with 1.5 % and 2.0 % [BMIM][CF₃SO₃] IL, about 100 times higher than for pristine SPEEK [159].

2.2.4. Flame retardancy and self-lubricating properties

ILs have been employed in combination with epoxy resins to impart specific functionalities to the polymeric networks such as flame retardancy or self-lubricating properties. Phosphorus-based ILs have been used as curing agent and flame retardant in epoxy polymers. The presence of phosphorus alters the pyrolysis mechanism and promotes charring that protects the polymer. According to the reported results, the peak of heat release rate and the total heat release

decreased by 73% and 48% respectively, when using tributyl(ethyl)phosphonium diethylphosphate (named IL169) [160]. An increase in the IL content increased the phosphorus content in char and, thus, the graphitization and the thermo-oxidative stability of the char were improved. The expanded char protects the underlying polymer.

Another phosphonate-based ionic liquid, 1-vinyl-3-(diethoxyphosphoryl)-propylimidazolium bromide was used as flame-retardant for epoxy resin. The authors reported that with 4 wt% loading, the epoxy/IL composite showed a limiting oxygen index (LOI) value of 34.9%, higher than neat epoxy (26 %) (**Figure 44**) [161]. The char yield was also improved, and the peak of heat release rate was reduced significantly. Moreover, the incorporation of IL produced only slight changes in composite color and transparency and improved its mechanical properties. These results allow overcoming the drawbacks of traditional flame retardants which are known by altering the color and transparency of the resins as well as their mechanical properties as more than 10 wt% loadings are usually needed [161].

Figure 44. LOI values and UL-94 ratings of EP composites. EP/IL-*n* corresponds to an epoxy composite with the content of IL of *n* wt%. Reprinted with permission from [161].

ILs can also impart self-lubricating capacity to epoxy resins. Studies revealed that the addition of the tri-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)ammonium]] citrate to the prepolymer, promotes the reduction

of the residual curing enthalpy and the glass transition temperature ^[162]. The addition of the IL reduced the storage and loss modulus and caused a 50% reduction of the friction coefficient when compared to neat epoxy. The presence of IL protects the surface from damage, and the authors proposed a self-lubrication mechanism by the release of IL under load where the surface cavities are healed after the release resulting in a polished surface ^[162].

1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate has also been used to improve the tribological properties of epoxy resins and their lubrication. This IL was also used in combination with single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) ^[163]. The best results were obtained when using both SWCNT and ILs, as additives. The composite produced a friction reduction and antiwear performance, together with an acceleration of the curing process and an increase of cross-linking density ^[163]. The self-healing ability over time increased with increasing IL content, with good recovery rates and a total self-repair after 22 h ^[163-164]. The molecular interaction between the polymer and the charged species of the IL, and the increased chain mobility and the curing capacity of the IL seemed to be responsible for the self-healing.

2.2.5. Biomedical applications

The incorporation of ILs into a polymer matrix has been emerged as an exciting approach in biomedical applications mainly due to the participation of ionic charges from the IL into cell stimulation. This enables that, in many cases under an electrical stimulus, the separation of the ionic charges potentiates the *in vitro* cell adhesion and, in this sense, the cell proliferation.

PVDF electrospun fibers containing [EMIM][TFSI] have been prepared for tissue engineering applications ^[24]. Randomly distributed and aligned fibers were obtained with an average diameter between 700 and 500 nm (**Figure 45**).

Figure 45. Morphology of polymer electrospun fiber mats: a) random neat PVDF, b) aligned neat PVDF, c) random PVDF with 5 wt% IL, and d) aligned PVDF with 5 wt% IL. Reprinted with permission from ^[24].

The IL structure induced the crystallization of PVDF fibers in the piezoelectric β -phase, and full crystallization was obtained when using 10 wt% IL. Biocompatibility tests revealed the non-cytotoxicity of the prepared materials demonstrating their good potential for biomedical applications, while both the fiber orientation and the IL content affected the cell viability (**Figure 46**) ^[24].

Figure 46. a) Cytotoxicity assay of C2C12 cells in contact with the as-prepared extraction media exposed to PVDF fibers with different orientation and ionic liquid concentrations for 24 and 72 h. Relative cell viability was presented as the percentage of control ($n = 4$) \pm SD. b-c) Images of C2C12 cell morphology incubated for 24 h in the extraction medium of (b) control and (c) oriented PVDF fibers with 5 wt% ionic liquid concentration. The magnification is 940 for all images. Reprinted with permission from [24].

In a radically different application, a polymer electrolyte-enabled biocompatible magnesium-air battery device was developed to use in miniaturized implanted medical devices (IMDs) [165]. The biocompatible electrolyte was made of chitosan, a biopolymer, and the IL choline nitrate ([Ch][NO₃]). The anode of the electrode was composed of a bioresorbable MG-alloy and the cathode of a biocompatible polypyrrole-toluene-4-sulfonic (PPy-pTS) film. The polymer/IL electrolyte offered a high ionic conductivity of $8.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and the final assembled device had a maximum volumetric power density of 3.9 W L^{-1} capable of driving small IMDs such as pacemakers and biomonitoring systems (**Figure 47**).

Figure 47. Electrochemical impedance spectra of Mg–air batteries before and after discharge at a current density of $20 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ for 6 h using CS–[Ch][NO₃] (1:5) film a) and PBS solution b) as electrolytes. Reprinted with permission from ^[165].

Stretchable ILs-based sensors aiming at the identification of the wrist pulses and with the ability to be woven with commercial rubber bands into bracelets for the detection of the hand gesture have been developed ^[166]. The sensors show outstanding performance like tunable sensitivity detection - 0.1% -500% of wide range strains, high long-term stability, and durability. These sensors are able to detect the cervical movements through the interface with the wireless circuit **(Figure 48)** ^[166].

Figure 48. Stretchable ILs-based sensor monitoring in real-time of wrist pulses, hand gestures and cervical movements. (a) Wrist pulse monitoring. Plots of resistance change of the sensor as a function of time (input voltage: 3v) (b) Monitoring different hand gestures by the bracelet weaved with ILs-based rubber band sensor. Characteristic current changes to respective hand motions (input voltage: 3v): (I) Clenching, (II) Thumb bending, (III) Forefinger bending, (IV) Little finger bending, (V) Palm bending. (c-f) IL-based sensor patches for cervical movements monitoring. (c) Schematic of sensor design for cervical spondylosis according to the strain directions of the skin during different neck movements. (d-f) The monitoring process of the movement of looking left. The number of the middle bubble which indicated the movement of

looking left changed obviously from 80 to 68, and then back to 80 when the volunteer turned back his head. Reprinted with permission from [166].

Highly transparent, and ultra-stretchable ionic conductors based on polymeric gelators [poly(methyl methacrylate-ran-butyl acrylate), PMMA-*r*-PBA] and the IL [EMIM][TFSI] also received special attention as ionic sensors platforms for wearable electronics for biomedical applications as a skin-type strain sensor, referred as ionoskin [167]. The developed gels presented interesting mechanical properties such as elongation limit $\approx 850\%$, elastic modulus $\approx 3.1 \times 10^5$ Pa), and a recovery ratio of $\approx 96.1\%$ after 500 stretching/releasing cycles gels. These properties are suitable for envisaging sensor applications. Attaching these gels to a part of the human body is possible to monitor several human movements (**Figure 49**) [167].

Figure 49. a) Schematic illustration of the practical application of ionoskin. The insets display photographs of devices applied to finger, elbow, ankle, and knee. Relative resistance changes of the ionoskin adhered to the b) finger, c) elbow, d) knee and e) ankle for which various movements were successfully monitored. Reprinted with permission from ^[167].

2.2.6. Additional applications

The effect of two ILs, [AMIM][Cl] and [EMIM][BF₄], on the properties of methyl vinyl silicone rubber (MVQ) were evaluated ^[168]. MVQ possess high and low-temperature performance, electrical insulation, high resistance and, thus, have found widely used for high-tech applications in aviation, the aerospace industry, electronics, etc. However, it generates static electricity, a significant drawback for this type of applications. To reduce the static electricity and increase the performance of MVQ-materials for high-tech applications, ILs were incorporated into the MVQ matrix ^[168]. Composites using [EMIM][BF₄] showed lower surface and volume resistivities than the ones using [AMIM][Cl]. The incorporation of ILs slightly reduced the mechanical properties of the composites, and with increasing [EMIM][BF₄] content, the surface and volume resistivities as well as the water contact angle decreased. Also, [AMIM][Cl] reduced the transparency and altered the color of MVQ due to the decomposition of the IL, whereas this effect was not observed for [EMIM][BF₄]. MVQ/[EMIM][BF₄] composites using 2.0 phr displayed better antistatic performance with lower surface and volume resistivities. The authors reported that the antistatic mechanism was related to the synergistic effect of ionic migration and moisture absorption.

Polymer-based transistors have been prepared using physically cross-linked PVDF-based ion gels. These gels were prepared by crystallization of the polymer in [EMIM][TFSI] (**Figure 50**) ^[169].

Figure 50. a) Chemical structures of PVDF and [EMIM][TFSI]. b) Schematic illustration of the homopolymer ion gel. c) Optical images of solvent-cast bulk (top) and spin-coated thin gels (bottom). In the picture, EMIM is the same as EMI. Reprinted with permission from ^[169].

The composites showed an elastic mechanical response and excellent ionic conductivity ($2.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) and a specific capacitance of $25 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$. The PVDF crystals acted as physical cross-links to produce a 3D gel. These ion gels were successfully applied to organic thin-film transistors as high-capacitance gate dielectrics ^[169].

The effect of the addition of titanium dioxide nanoparticles to PVDF-HFP and [BMIM][BF₄] IL containing membranes was also investigated for the fabrication of electric double-layer capacitor cells. The capacitive properties were confirmed, and the specific capacitance was 147.66 F g^{-1} at a current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} , a significantly higher value when comparing with nanoparticle free membranes ^[104].

Table 3 Summary the ILs polymer composites as advanced functional materials and its applicability.

Table 3- ILs polymer composites as advanced functional materials.

Application	Polymer	IL	Ref.
Photo and thermo-responsive	ABC(azo) triblock copolymer	[EMIM][TFSI]	[33]
	Poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM)	[P66614][DCA] [EMIM][ESO ₄]	[34]
	PU	[BMIM][TFSI] [BDMIM][TFSI] [EMIM][TFSI] [HMIM][TFSI]	[39]
	PVDF-HFP	[EMIM][DCA] [EMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][BF ₄]	[170]
		[EMIM][BTI]	[30a]
		[EMIM][TFSI]	[30d, 32, 132]
		[BMIM][TFSI]	[30e]
	PVDF-HFP PMMA-PS	[EMIM][TFSI]	[41b]
	PEGDMA	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[41c] [41a]
	PS-b-PMMA-b-PS	[EMIM][TFSI]	[30f, 31]
	PVA PVP PEG	[EMIM][TFSI]	[171]
	PVDF	[BMIM] ₂ [NiCl ₄]	[38]
	Polystyrene-block-poly(methyl methacrylate)-blockpolystyrene (SMS, 17K-86K-17K) triblock copolymer	[EMIM][TFSI]	[28]
	Copolymer of PS	[EMIM][TFSI]	[29]
	PS-r-PMMA	[EMIM][TFSI]	[172]
	Poly(methyl methacrylate)-b-polystyrene) ₆ ((MS) ₆)	[EMIM][TFSI]	[173]
	P(S-r-BzMA-r-MMA)	[EMIM][TFSI] [EMIM][PF ₆] [P12][PF ₆]	[35]
	PMMA-r-PBA	[EMIM][TFSI]	[167]
Optical materials	PMMA	[BMPyr][TFSI]	[27]
	PDMS	[EMIM][CF ₃ SO ₃]	[55]
pH sensitive	PVC	CPFP	[42]
Sensors	Acrylate polymers	[BACO][EA] [EMIM][BF ₄]	[44]
		[EMIM][TCB] [EMIM][BF ₄]	[174] [175]
	PEDOT	[BMIM][Cl]	[46]
	Prepolymer	[EMIM][BF ₄]	[44]
	PEGDA	[EMIM][TFSI] [EMPY][TFSI] [BMPYRR][TFSI] [P ₁₄₄₄][TFSI] [N ₄₁₁₁][TFSI]	[176]
		[BMIM][TFSI]	[177]
		[BMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][DCA] [BMIM][BF ₄]	[178] [64] [67]
	PSF	TEAF TEAA	[73]

	TPU	[BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][NO ₃] [BMIM][TFSI]	[179]
	PVDF-HFP	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[180]
	PEGDME	[P66614][2-Op]	[181]
	PMDA-ODA	[BMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][Tfo]	[182]
	PIM-1 copolymer PEG	[EMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][TFSI] [HMIM][TFSI]	[183]
	PES	[EMIM][TFSI]	[184]
	Polyimide (PI)	[BMIM][TFSI]	[185]
	PU	[BMIM][Cl] [BMIM][BF ₄] [EOHMIM][Gly]	[75]
	PU/PBA/IL-PEG	IL-Cl IL-Br	[47]
Actuators	PVDF	[HMIM][Cl] [HMIM][TFSI]	[186]
		[EMIM][TFSI] [HMIM][TFSI] [C ₁₀ MIM][TFSI] [EMIM][Cl] [HMIM][Cl] [C ₁₀ MIM][Cl]	[50]
		[N _{1112OH}][TFSI] [EMIM][ESO ₄]	[22b]
		[EMIM][TFSI]	[22a]
	PVDF PVDF-HFP PVDF-TrFE PVDF-CTFE		
	Nafion	[EMIM][Tfo]	[187]
		[EMIM][Tfo] [EMIM][Im]	[188]
		[EMIM][Tfo]	[51]
	PVDF-HFP	[EMIM][BF ₄] [EMIM][Tfo]	[52]
	SPI	[EMIM][TFSI]	[53]
Air remediation	Pebax 1657	[BMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][DCA] [BMIM][BF ₄]	[189]
		[BMIM][BF ₄]	[64]
			[67]
	SPI	[BMIM][TFSI] [BMIM][PF ₆]	[68]
	PBI PMDA-ODAPI	[BMIM][TFSI]	[69] [70]
	PSF	[EMIM][TFSI] [EMIM][CF ₃ SO ₃]	[71]
	PEG	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[74]
	PU	[BMIM][Cl] [BMIM][BF ₄] [EOHMIM][Gly]	[75]

	PVA PPy PAM	[C ₈ MIM] ₃ [La(NO ₃) ₆] [C ₈ MIM] ₂ [Eu(NO ₃) ₅]	[76]	
	Nafion	[TMA][OH]	[77]	
Water remediation	Vinyl polymer-silica	[BVMIM][Br]	[78]	
	Poly (ionic liquid)	dimethyl-dodecyl-4-vinyl benzyl ammonium chloride (monomer)	[79]	
	Cellulose	1-methylimidazole (monomer)	[80]	
	PAMDA	[AMIM][Cl]	[82]	
	PDVB	1-aminoethyl-3- vinylimidazolium chloride hydrochloride	[83]	
	Chitosan	[BMIM][Cl] [CMIM][Cl]	[81]	
Batteries and fuel cells	PVDF PEG	Imidazolium ILs family	[106]	
	PVDF-TrFE	[N _{1,1,2,0H}][TFSI]	[113]	
	PVDF-HFP	[EMIM][BF ₄] [Li][BF ₄]	[107]	
		[DEMM][TFSI]	[108]	
		[PMIM][TFSI] [Li][TFSI]	[114]	
		[EMIM][BF ₄] [EMIM][Tf] [BMIM][PF ₆]	[117]	
		[P13][TFSI] [Li][TFSI] [EMIM][TFSI] [PMMI][TFSI] [PP13][TFSI]	[26b]	
		[DMOIM][Tf]	[149]	
		[Li][TFSI] [EMI][TFSI]	[119]	
		[EMIM][Tfo]	[120]	
		[DMOIM][TFSI]	[148]	
		[EMIM][TFSI] [EMIM][BF ₄]	[190]	
		[EMIM][TCB]	[191]	
		[BMIM][BF ₄]	[192]	
		[EMIM][TFSI]	[193]	
		[PP1201][TFSI]	[194]	
		[HMIM][TFSI]	[195]	
		[Li][TFSI] [PMMI][TFSI]	[118]	
		[MPn][TFSI] [MPz][TFSI] [MPy][TFSI] [MIM][TFSI] [EIM][TFSI]	[196]	
		PEG	[EMIM][TFSI] [Li][TFSI]	[121]
			[BMIM][Tfo] [EMIM][Tfo]	[123]
			[EMIM][Tfo] [EMIM][TFSI]	[136]
	[Py _{r14}][TFSI] [Li][TFSI]		[122]	
	PEG	[Li][Tf] [BMP][FSI]	[124]	

		[EMIM][FSI] [PMP][FSI] [BMP][TFSI] [EMIM][TFSI]	
	Polyimides (PI)	[Li][TFSI] [BMIM][TFSI]	[127]
	ENR	[EMIM][Cl]	[54]
	HPMC	[BMIM][Tfo]	[130]
	HEC	[EMIM][Tfo]	[131]
	Chitosan	[NbmD][OH]	[150]
	PLA	[Pyr ₁₄][TFSI]	[133]
	Polyethylene	[MTO][IM] TTDPP	[197]
	PVDF PVA	PP ₁₄	[160]
	PAN-r-PB	[BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][Tfo] [EMIM][Tfo] [HMIM][PF ₆] [4MBP][BF ₄] [BDMIM][BF ₄] [OMIM][PF ₆] [C ₁₀ MIM][PF ₆] [C ₁₂ MIM][PF ₆] [HPy][PF ₆]	[134]
	PVA	[BMIM][I]	[198]
	HBPS-(PMMA-b-PPEGMA)	[BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][PF ₆] [Li][TFSI]	[3]
	PPy	[VCMIM][Cl] [SBVIM][HSO ₄]	[199]
	PPO	Me-IL Ethyl-IL Hydroxyethyl-IL	[151]
	Vinyl monomers	[VBIM][TFSI]	[152]
	Nafion	[HMI][FAP] [BMPyr][FAP] [HMI][BTSE] [BMPyr][BTSE] [BMIM][PF ₆] [DMBuIm][H ₂ PO ₄] [DEMA][Tfo] [C ₃ OHMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][BF ₄]	[155] [156] [153] [154]
	Nafion Hyflon	[BMI][BTI]	[157]
	SPEEK	[BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][CF ₃ SO ₃] [C ₁₀ MIM][CF ₃ SO ₃] [BMI][BF ₄] [BMIM][Tfo] [BMM][BF ₄] [BMIM][Tfo] [BMIM][Cl] [DEMA][Tfo] [EIM][Tfo] [DEMA][Tfo] [DEMA][Tfo] [BMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][TFSI]	[158] [159] [137] [138] [139] [200] [141] [201] [202]

	SPEEK	TFAPA	[203]
	PVDF	[BMIM][PF ₆] [BMIM][H ₂ PO ₄]	[204]
	PVDF	[EMIM][TFSI]	[205]
	PEG	[BMIM][TFSI]	[206]
	PANI	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[207]
	Polyfluorene	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[208]
	PVA	[BMIM][Cl] [BMIM][Br] [BMIM][I] [BMIM][I]	[209] [210]
	PAN	[BMIM][TFSI]	[211]
	PVDF	[EMIM][TFSI]	[212]
	PEG	[EMIM][Tfo]	[213]
	PU Polybutadiene (BR)	[BMIM][PF ₆] [BMIM][MDEGSO ₄] [MOIM][Cl]	[214]
	PEDOT:PSS	[EMIM][TFSI]	[215]
	PBI	DC3 MC6	[216]
	PVDF PEG	[Li][TFSI]	[217]
	PVA PAA	[Li][TFSI]	[218]
	Sulfonated tetrafluoroethylene based fluoropolymer-copolymer, Nafion	[BMIM][Tf] [BMIM][BF ₄]	[219]
	Methyl methacrylate, acrylonitrile, vinyl acetate, styrene and 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate	[EMIM][BF ₄] [BP][BF ₄]	[220]
	PVP	[EMIM][BF ₄] [BMIM][PF ₆] [OMIM][N(SO ₂ CF ₃) ₂]	[221]
Flame retardancy or self-lubricating properties	Epoxy	IL169	[160]
		1-vinyl-3-(diethoxyphosphoryl)-propylimidazolium bromide	[161]
		tri-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)ammonium)]	[162]
		[C ₈ MIM][BF ₄]	[163-164]
Biomedical applications	PVDF	[EMIM][TFSI]	[24]
	Chitosan	[Ch][NO ₃]	[165]
	PMMA	[HMIM][TFSI]	[222]
	PEG	[HMIM][TFSI]	[223]
	PHB	[EMIM][TFSI]	[56]
Transistors	PVDF	[EMIM][TFSI]	[169]
	PVDF-HFP	[BMIM][BF ₄]	[104]
	PVA	[HOEtMIM]Cl	[224]
High tech applications	MVQ	[AMIM][Cl] [EMIM][BF ₄]	[168]
Solar cells	PVDF	[EMIM][TFSI]	[225]
Dehydration of isopropanol	PVA	[BMIM][Cl] [HMIM][BF ₄] [C ₈ MIM][Cl]	[226]

3. Final remarks, conclusions, and main challenges

ILs have emerged as a highly interesting alternative in the development of advanced smart and functional materials due to its unique characteristics and functionalities. The selection of the appropriate cation and anion as well as a suitable polymer matrix promotes the development of new ionic materials with superior properties for specific applications. The IL/polymer materials can be processed into distinct morphologies such as gels, films, membranes, and fibers with potential applications in several fields.

Despite the increasing growth in the development of IL/polymer matrixes, some ILs functionalities are starting to be explored such as the optical properties and the magneto-ionic effect, and its potentiality has already been demonstrated in areas such as sensors and actuators, printing technologies, and biomedical applications, environmental applications, among other interesting functionalities of the ILs.

It is relevant to notice that the magnetic functionality of the ILs can be used in the stimulation of animal cells. Moreover, the combination of electroactive polymers requires further and deeper investigation. In this sense, the main challenges of ILs based materials, rely on the synergistically interplay between IL and polymer matrix, which can improve the efficiency of the materials and generate new applications. In this context, theoretical simulations need to be performed to get a better comprehension about the IL-polymer interactions, and IL-solvent interactions. It is also paramount to increase the number of studies concerning the potentiality of the developed materials for biomedical applications through cytotoxicity studies of the IL/polymer materials. In this case, the influence of the ionic charges of the IL in the cell behavior demands further studies using *in vitro* and even *in vivo* assays.

The potential that IL have for environmental remediation is enormous. The IL properties, as well as the nature of the pollutant and other experimental conditions, affect the process efficiency. The adsorption capacity is usually enhanced through electrostatic attraction between the contaminant and the adsorption sites when ILs are added to the materials. The literature

lacks reports on the specificity of the adsorption process when using more than one pollutant, which may be relevant envisaging real applications. Moreover, the regeneration process should be investigated as the reusability of material has a massive impact on the process costs. Moreover, in the framework of environmental remediation, there are other processes such as photocatalysis that should receive further attention. There are already some exciting materials developed with ILs for application in suspension, but there is a lack of immobilized photocatalytic materials with ILs, which would allow reutilization and reduce costs and secondary pollution.

In the field of actuators, significant efforts need to be performed in the performance of the actuator, namely the produced force and actuators stability over time. Another interesting point of view relies on the development of new IL/polymer composites based on natural polymers that will reduce the environmental impact of the produced materials. This last issue is transversal and relevant in all applications, from sensors and actuators to biomedical and energy applications.

In the area of lithium-ion batteries, the most explored area of application, ILs have emerged as a potential candidate to replace conventional electrolyte and solid polymer electrolytes, addressing the safety issue without compromise the high ionic conductivity above $10^{-3} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ and excellent thermal and mechanical properties.

Due to the high interest in the technological transfer, and the potential applicability of these materials, the upscale to printing technologies will be a necessary step.

4. Acknowledgments

The authors thank the FCT (Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia) for financial support under the framework of the Strategic Funding UID/FIS/04650/2019 and projects PTDC/BTM-MAT/28237/2017, PTDC/EMD-EMD/28159/2017 and PTDC/FIS-MAC/28157/2017. Funds

provided by FCT in the framework of EuroNanoMed 2016 call, Project LungChek ENMed/0049/2016 are also gratefully acknowledged. D.M.C, L.C.F and C.M.C also thanks to the FCT for the grants SFRH/BPD/121526/2016, SFRH/BD/145345/2019 and SFRH/BPD/112547/2015, respectively. PMM thanks to the ENMed_CQ_CF_04_2018 grant. Finally, the authors acknowledge funding by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) through the project MAT2016-76039-C4-3-R (AEI/FEDER, UE) and from the Basque Government Industry and Education Departments under the ELKARTEK, HAZITEK and PIBA (PIBA-2018-06) programs, respectively.

4. References

- [1] S. G. Zhang, Q. H. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Z. J. Chen, M. Watanabe, Y. Q. Deng, *Progress in Materials Science* **2016**, 77, 80.
- [2] a) R. L. Vekariya, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2017**, 227, 44; b) Z. Lei, B. Chen, Y.-M. Koo, D. R. MacFarlane, *Chemical Reviews* **2017**, 117, 6633.
- [3] A. L. Wang, H. Xu, Q. Zhou, X. Liu, Z. Y. Li, R. Gao, X. F. Liu, L. Y. Zhang, *J. Solid State Electrochem.* **2017**, 21, 2355.
- [4] a) K. Dong, X. Liu, H. Dong, X. Zhang, S. Zhang, *Chemical Reviews* **2017**, 117, 6636; b) B. Wang, L. Qin, T. Mu, Z. Xue, G. Gao, *Chemical Reviews* **2017**, 117, 7113.
- [5] R. D. Rogers, K. R. Seddon, *Science* **2003**, 302, 792.
- [6] Y.-S. Ye, J. Rick, B.-J. Hwang, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2013**, 1, 2719.
- [7] K. N. Marsh, J. A. Boxall, R. Lichtenthaler, *Fluid Phase Equilibria* **2004**, 219, 93.
- [8] G. Yu, D. Zhao, L. Wen, S. Yang, X. Chen, *Aiche Journal* **2012**, 58, 2885.
- [9] a) F. Endres, *Ionic Liquids: Promising Solvents for Electrochemistry*, **2004**; b) H. Niedermeyer, J. P. Hallett, I. J. Villar-Garcia, P. A. Hunt, T. Welton, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2012**, 41, 7780.
- [10] a) C. G. Yoo, Y. Q. Pu, A. J. Ragauskas, *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* **2017**, 5, 5; b) P. C. Marr, A. C. Marr, *Green Chemistry* **2016**, 18, 105.
- [11] H. Taherifard, S. Raeissi, *Journal of Chemical and Engineering Data* **2016**, 61, 4031.
- [12] a) D. M. Correia, R. Sabater i Serra, J. A. Gómez Tejedor, V. de Zea Bermudez, A. Andrio Balado, J. M. Meseguer-Dueñas, J. L. Gomez Ribelles, S. Lanceros-Méndez, C. M. Costa, *Polymer* **2018**, 143, 164; b) M. Armand, F. Endres, D. R. MacFarlane, H. Ohno, B. Scrosati, *Nature Materials* **2009**, 8, 621.
- [13] a) J. Luczak, M. Paszkiewicz, A. Krukowska, A. Malankowska, A. Zaleska-Medynska, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **2016**, 230, 13; b) N. L. Mai, K. Ahn, Y. M. Koo, *Process Biochemistry* **2014**, 49, 872.
- [14] J. M. S. S. Esperanca, J. N. Canongia Lopes, M. Tariq, L. M. N. B. F. Santos, J. W. Magee, L. P. N. Rebelo, *Journal of Chemical and Engineering Data* **2010**, 55, 3.
- [15] a) H. Watanabe, H. Doi, S. Saito, M. Matsugami, K. Fujii, R. Kanzaki, Y. Kameda, Y. Umebayashi, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2016**, 217, 35; b) S. Zhang, K. Dokko, M. Watanabe, *Chemistry of Materials* **2014**, 26, 2915.
- [16] S. Kazemiabnavi, Z. Zhang, K. Thornton, S. Banerjee, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2016**, 120, 5691.
- [17] a) W. G. Drossel, F. Meinel, A. Bucht, H. Kunze, *Procedia Manufacturing* **2018**, 21, 197; b) A. Kumar, A. Srivastava, I. Y. Galaev, B. Mattiasson, *Progress in Polymer Science* **2007**, 32, 1205.
- [18] Y. Kitazawa, K. Ueno, M. Watanabe, *The Chemical Record* **2018**, 18, 391.
- [19] D. M. Correia, C. M. Costa, E. Lizundia, R. Sabater i Serra, J. A. Gómez-Tejedor, L. T. Biosca, J. M. Meseguer-Dueñas, J. L. Gomez Ribelles, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2019**, 123, 27917.
- [20] D. M. Correia, J. C. Barbosa, C. M. Costa, P. M. Reis, J. M. S. S. Esperança, V. de Zea Bermudez, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2019**, 123, 12744.
- [21] D. M. Correia, L. C. Fernandes, C. García-Astrain, M. Tariq, J. M. S. S. Esperança, V. de Zea Bermudez, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Composites Part B: Engineering* **2019**, 178.
- [22] a) J. C. Dias, D. M. Correia, C. M. Costa, C. Ribeiro, A. Maceiras, J. L. Vilas, G. Botelho, V. de Zea Bermudez, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 296, 598; b) J. C. Dias, M. S. Martins, S. Ribeiro, M. M. Silva, J. Esperanca, C. Ribeiro, G. Botelho, C. M. Costa, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Journal of Materials Science* **2016**, 51, 9490; c) L. Fernandes, D. M. Correia, N. Pereira, C. Tubio, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *ACS Applied Polymer Materials* **2019**, DOI: 10.1021/acsapm.9b00675.
- [23] a) C. Ribeiro, V. Sencadas, D. M. Correia, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* **2015**, 136, 46; b) D. M. Correia, C. Ribeiro, V. Sencadas, L. Vikingsson, M. Oliver Gasch, J. L. Gómez Ribelles, G. Botelho, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Materials & Design* **2016**, 92, 674.

- [24] J. C. Dias, D. C. Correia, A. C. Lopes, S. Ribeiro, C. Ribeiro, V. Sencadas, G. Botelho, J. Esperanca, J. M. Laza, J. L. Vilas, L. M. Leon, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Journal of Materials Science* **2016**, 51, 4442.
- [25] a) C. M. Costa, A. California, V. F. Cardoso, V. Sencadas, L. C. Rodrigues, M. M. Silva, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Ferroelectrics* **2012**, 430, 103; b) C. M. Costa, M. M. Silva, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *RSC Advances* **2013**, 3, 11404.
- [26] a) S. Ferrari, E. Quartarone, P. Mustarelli, A. Magistris, M. Fagnoni, S. Protti, C. Gerbaldi, A. Spinella, *Journal of Power Sources* **2010**, 195, 559; b) H. Ye, J. Huang, J. J. Xu, A. Khalfan, S. G. Greenbaum, *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **2007**, 154, A1048.
- [27] K. P. S. Hussan, M. S. Thayyil, S. K. Deshpande, T. V. Jinita, J. Kolte, *Solid State Ion.* **2017**, 310, 166.
- [28] H. C. Moon, T. P. Lodge, C. D. Frisbie, *Chemistry of Materials* **2015**, 27, 1420.
- [29] D. G. Seo, H. C. Moon, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2018**, 28, 1706948.
- [30] a) B.-H. Chen, S.-Y. Kao, C.-W. Hu, M. Higuchi, K.-C. Ho, Y.-C. Liao, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2015**, 7, 25069; b) S.-Y. Kao, H.-C. Lu, C.-W. Kung, H.-W. Chen, T.-H. Chang, K.-C. Ho, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2016**, 8, 4175; c) Y. Alesanco, A. Viñuales, J. Palenzuela, I. Odriozola, G. Cabañero, J. Rodriguez, R. Tena-Zaera, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2016**, 8, 14795; d) H. Oh, D. G. Seo, T. Y. Yun, C. Y. Kim, H. C. Moon, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 7658; e) H. Oh, J. K. Lee, Y. M. Kim, T. Y. Yun, U. Jeong, H. C. Moon, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 45959; f) H. C. Moon, T. P. Lodge, C. D. Frisbie, *Chemistry of Materials* **2014**, 26, 5358.
- [31] H. C. Moon, T. P. Lodge, C. D. Frisbie, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2014**, 136, 3705.
- [32] K. Hong, Y. K. Kwon, J. Ryu, J. Y. Lee, S. H. Kim, K. H. Lee, *Scientific Reports* **2016**, 6, 29805.
- [33] R. Tamate, R. Usui, K. Hashimoto, Y. Kitazawa, H. Kokubo, M. Watanabe, *Soft Matter* **2018**, 14, 9088.
- [34] N. Gil-Gonzalez, T. Akyazi, E. Castano, F. Benito-Lopez, M. C. Morant-Minana, *Sensors and Actuators B-Chemical* **2018**, 260, 380.
- [35] D. G. Seo, Y. M. Kim, H. Ahn, H. C. Moon, *Nanoscale* **2019**, 11, 16733.
- [36] X. Wei, L. Yu, D. Wang, X. Jin, G. Z. Chen, *Green Chemistry* **2008**, 10, 296.
- [37] X. Wei, L. Yu, X. Jin, D. Wang, G. Z. Chen, *Advanced Materials* **2008**, 21, 776.
- [38] L. C. Fernandes, D. M. Correia, C. García-Astrain, N. Pereira, M. Tariq, J. M. S. S. Esperança, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 20316.
- [39] H. Y. Lee, Y. Cai, S. Velioglu, C. Mu, C. J. Chang, Y. L. Chen, Y. Song, J. W. Chew, X. M. Hu, *Chemistry of Materials* **2017**, 29, 6947.
- [40] H. Cheng, X. He, Z. Fan, J. Ouyang, *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, 9, 1901085.
- [41] a) I. H. Sajid, M. F. M. Sabri, S. M. Said, M. F. M. Salleh, N. N. N. Ghazali, R. Saidur, B. Subramaniam, S. W. Hasan, H. A. Jaffery, *Energy Conversion and Management* **2019**, 198, 111813; b) D. Zhao, A. Martinelli, A. Willfahrt, T. Fischer, D. Bernin, Z. U. Khan, M. Shahi, J. Brill, M. P. Jonsson, S. Fabiano, X. Crispin, *Nature Communications* **2019**, 10, 1093; c) I. H. Sajid, N. Aslfattahi, M. F. Mohd Sabri, S. M. Said, R. Saidur, M. F. Mohd Salleh, N. N. Nik Ghazali, S. W. Hasan, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 320, 134575.
- [42] J. Ping, Y. Wang, J. Wu, Y. Ying, F. Ji, *Microchimica Acta* **2012**, 176, 229.
- [43] D. M. Correia, P. Martins, M. Tariq, J. M. S. S. Esperança, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Nanoscale* **2018**, 10, 15747.
- [44] J. Lee, M. O. F. Emon, M. Vatani, J. W. Choi, *Smart Mater. Struct.* **2017**, 26, 8.
- [45] M. O. F. Emon, J. W. Choi, *Sensors* **2017**, 17.
- [46] Kuei-Fei Lai, Wan-Yu Su, Wei-Ting Chang, S.-H. Cheng, *International Journal of Electrochemical Science* **2013**, 8, 7959.
- [47] Y. Zhang, J. Xiang, Z. Hu, J. Lei, C. Zhou, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **2014**, 131.
- [48] J. Wang, C. Y. Xu, M. Taya, Y. Kuga, *Smart Materials & Structures* **2007**, 16, S214.
- [49] P. Martins, A. C. Lopes, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Progress in Polymer Science* **2014**, 39, 683.

- [50] R. Mejri, J. C. Dias, S. B. Hentati, G. Botelho, J. Esperanca, C. M. Costa, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2016**, 85, 445.
- [51] A. Almomani, W. Y. J. Hong, W. Hong, R. Montazami, *Polymers* **2017**, 9, 13.
- [52] T. Sugino, Y. Shibata, K. Kiyohara, K. Asaka, *Sensors and Actuators B-Chemical* **2018**, 273, 955.
- [53] S. Imaizumi, Y. Ohtsuki, T. Yasuda, H. Kokubo, M. Watanabe, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2013**, 5, 6307.
- [54] S. Matchawet, A. Kaesaman, N. Vennemann, C. Kumerlowe, C. Nakason, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2017**, 87, 344.
- [55] N. Terasawa, *Sensors and Actuators B-Chemical* **2018**, 257, 815.
- [56] L. Migliorini, T. Santaniello, S. Rondinini, P. Saettone, M. Comes Franchini, C. Lenardi, P. Milani, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* **2019**, 286, 230.
- [57] J. C. G. Sousa, A. R. Ribeiro, M. O. Barbosa, M. F. R. Pereira, A. M. T. Silva, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2018**, 344, 146.
- [58] a) J. Monisha, T. Tenzin, A. Naresh, B. M. Blessy, N. B. Krishnamurthy, *Interdisciplinary Toxicology* **2014**, 7, 60; b) M. E. Mahmoud, M. M. Osman, A. A. Yakout, A. M. Abdelfattah, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2018**, 266, 834.
- [59] X. Yan, S. Anguille, M. Bendahan, P. Moulin, *Separation and Purification Technology* **2019**, 222, 230.
- [60] J. A. Ritter, presented at The 2008 Annual Meeting **2008**.
- [61] A. Ayati, S. Ranjbari, B. Tanhaei, M. Sillanpää, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2019**, 275, 71.
- [62] N. MacDowell, N. Florin, A. Buchard, J. Hallett, A. Galindo, G. Jackson, C. S. Adjiman, C. K. Williams, N. Shah, P. Fennell, *Energy & Environmental Science* **2010**, 3, 1645.
- [63] M. D. Li, X. P. Zhang, S. J. Zeng, L. Bai, H. S. Gao, J. Deng, Q. Y. Yang, S. J. Zhang, *Rsc Advances* **2017**, 7, 6422.
- [64] E. G. Estahbanati, M. Omidkh, A. E. Amooghin, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **2017**, 51, 77.
- [65] N. M. Simon, M. Zanatta, J. Neumann, A.-L. Girard, G. Marin, H. Stassen, J. Dupont, *ChemPhysChem* **2018**, 19, 2879.
- [66] H. Rabiee, A. Ghadimi, T. Mohammadi, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, 476, 286.
- [67] W. Fam, J. Mansouri, H. Y. Li, V. Chen, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2017**, 537, 54.
- [68] A. Ito, T. Yasuda, X. F. Ma, M. Watanabe, *Polymer Journal* **2017**, 49, 671.
- [69] D. R. Pesiri, B. Jorgensen, R. C. Dye, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2003**, 218, 11.
- [70] L. Z. Liang, Q. Gan, P. Nancarrow, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, 450, 407.
- [71] M. Mirarab, M. Sharifi, M. A. Ghayyem, F. Mirarab, *Fluid Phase Equilibria* **2014**, 371, 6.
- [72] L. M. C. Pereira, M. B. Oliveira, A. M. A. Dias, F. Llovel, L. F. Vega, P. J. Carvalho, J. A. P. Coutinho, *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* **2013**, 19, 299.
- [73] R. U. Rehman, S. Rafiq, N. Muhammad, A. L. Khan, A. U. Rehman, T. T. Liu, M. Saeed, F. Jamil, M. Ghauri, X. H. Gu, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **2017**, 134, 11.
- [74] W. G. Lee, S. W. Kang, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2019**, 356, 312.
- [75] M. F. Rojas, L. P. Miranda, A. M. Ramirez, K. P. Quintero, F. Bernard, S. Einloft, L. A. C. Diaz, *Fluid Phase Equilibria* **2017**, 452, 103.
- [76] K. X. Song, L. He, L. Zhang, G. H. Tao, *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **2018**, 5.
- [77] P. G. Ingole, M. I. Baig, W. Choi, X. An, W. K. Choi, J. D. Jeon, H. K. Lee, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* **2017**, 127, 45.
- [78] G. Zhu, G. Cheng, T. Lu, Z. Cao, L. Wang, Q. Li, J. Fan, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2019**, 373, 347.
- [79] H. Yang, J. Zhang, Y. Liu, L. Wang, L. Bai, L. Yang, D. Wei, W. Wang, Y. Niu, H. Chen, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2019**, 284, 383.
- [80] M. H. Beyki, M. Bayat, F. Shemirani, *Bioresource Technology* **2016**, 218, 326.
- [81] Y. Wei, W. Huang, Y. Zhou, S. Zhang, D. Hua, X. Zhu, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* **2013**, 62, 365.
- [82] Y. Jiang, F. Li, G. Ding, Y. Chen, Y. Liu, Y. Hong, P. Liu, X. Qi, L. Ni, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2015**, 455, 125.

- [83] H. Gao, Y. Wang, L. Zheng, *Journal of Environmental Management* **2014**, 137, 81.
- [84] R. A. Robinson, R. H. Stokes, *Annual Review of Physical Chemistry* **1957**, 8, 37.
- [85] G. A. Nazri, G. Pistoia, *Lithium Batteries: Science and Technology*, Springer, **2009**.
- [86] M. Galiński, A. Lewandowski, I. Stępiak, *Electrochimica Acta* **2006**, 51, 5567.
- [87] S. Tsuzuki, *ChemPhysChem* **2012**, 13, 1664.
- [88] E. Zygadło-Monikowska, Z. Florjańczyk, P. Kubisa, T. Biedroń, W. Sadurski, A. Puczyłowska, N. Langwald, J. Ostrowska, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **2014**, 39, 2943.
- [89] D. R. MacFarlane, N. Tachikawa, M. Forsyth, J. M. Pringle, P. C. Howlett, G. D. Elliott, J. H. Davis, M. Watanabe, P. Simon, C. A. Angell, *Energy & Environmental Science* **2014**, 7, 232.
- [90] a) Q. Yang, Z. Zhang, X.-G. Sun, Y.-S. Hu, H. Xing, S. Dai, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2018**, 47, 2020; b) P. J. Sideris, Y. Chen, M. Gobet, S. G. Greenbaum, *Phosphorus, Sulfur, and Silicon and the Related Elements* **2019**, 194, 292; c) M. Xiao, Y. Meng, C. Duan, F. Zhu, Y. Zhang, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* **2019**, 30, 6148.
- [91] D. Y. Oh, Y. J. Nam, K. H. Park, S. H. Jung, K. T. Kim, A. R. Ha, Y. S. Jung, *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, 9, 1802927.
- [92] Z. Liu, G. Li, A. Borodin, X. Liu, Y. Li, F. Endres, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2019**, 123, 10325.
- [93] a) W. Wang, T. Yang, S. Li, W. Fan, X. Zhao, C. Fan, L. Yu, S. Zhou, X. Zuo, R. Zeng, J. Nan, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 317, 146; b) F. Liang, J. Yu, D. wang, L. Dong, C. Ma, J. Chen, B. Yang, C. Zhu, Y. Gao, C. Li, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 307, 83.
- [94] a) F. Ma, Z. Zhang, W. Yan, X. Ma, D. Sun, Y. Jin, X. Chen, K. He, *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* **2019**, 7, 4675; b) H. Liu, H. Yu, *Journal of Materials Science & Technology* **2019**, 35, 674.
- [95] A. Manthiram, X. Yu, S. Wang, *Nature Reviews Materials* **2017**, 2, 16103.
- [96] A. A. Shamsuri, R. Daik, *Applications of ionic liquids and their mixtures for preparation of advanced polymer blends and composites: A short review*, **2015**.
- [97] A. Eftekhari, Y. Liu, P. Chen, *Journal of Power Sources* **2016**, 334, 221.
- [98] F. Yuan, S. Chi, S. Dong, X. Zou, S. Lv, L. Bao, J. Wang, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 294, 249.
- [99] A. Tsurumaki, H. Ohno, S. Panero, M. A. Navarra, *Electrochimica Acta* **2019**, 293, 160.
- [100] P. Jankowski, W. Wieczorek, P. Johansson, *Energy Storage Materials* **2019**, 20, 108.
- [101] Shalu, V. K. Singh, R. K. Singh, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2015**, 3, 7305.
- [102] A. R. Polu, H.-W. Rhee, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **2017**, 42, 7212.
- [103] C. Xing, J. You, Y. Li, J. Li, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2015**, 119, 21155.
- [104] S. Das, A. Ghosh, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2017**, 164, F1348.
- [105] J. Lu, F. Yan, J. Texter, *Progress in Polymer Science* **2009**, 34, 431.
- [106] P. Xu, W. J. Fu, Y. D. Hu, Y. S. Ding, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, 158, 1.
- [107] J. W. Tang, R. Muchakayala, S. H. Song, M. Wang, K. N. Kumar, *Polym. Test* **2016**, 50, 247.
- [108] A. Roy, B. Dutta, S. Bhattacharya, *Journal of Materials Science* **2016**, 51, 7814.
- [109] a) M. A. Ratner, D. F. Shriver, *Chemical Reviews* **1988**, 88, 109; b) J.-H. Shin, W. A. Henderson, S. Scaccia, P. P. Prosini, S. Passerini, *Journal of Power Sources* **2006**, 156, 560.
- [110] X. Chen, P. M. Vereecken, *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **2019**, 6, 1800899.
- [111] G. G. Eshetu, D. Mecerreyes, M. Forsyth, H. Zhang, M. Armand, *Molecular Systems Design & Engineering* **2019**, 4, 294.
- [112] N. I. B. Wafi, W. R. W. Daud, A. Ahmad, E. H. Majlan, M. R. Somalu, *Polymer Bulletin* **2019**, 76, 3693.
- [113] R. Leones, C. M. Costa, A. V. Machado, J. M. S. S. Esperança, M. M. Silva, S. Lanceros-Méndez, *Solid State Ion.* **2013**, 253, 143.
- [114] J.-K. Kim, A. Matic, J.-H. Ahn, P. Jacobsson, *Journal of Power Sources* **2010**, 195, 7639.
- [115] Y.-C. Tseng, Y. Wu, C.-H. Tsao, H. Teng, S.-S. Hou, J.-S. Jan, *Polymer* **2019**, 173, 110.
- [116] L. E. Shmukler, E. V. Glushenkova, Y. A. Fadeeva, M. S. Gruzdev, N. O. Kudryakova, L. P. Safonova, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2019**, 283, 338.
- [117] J. Fuller, A. C. Breda, R. T. Carlin, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1998**, 459, 29.

- [118] D. Zhang, R. Li, T. Huang, A. Yu, *Journal of Power Sources* **2010**, 195, 1202.
- [119] Q. Guo, Y. Han, H. Wang, S. Xiong, Y. Li, S. Liu, K. Xie, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* **2017**, DOI: 10.1021/acsami.7b12092.
- [120] G. P. Pandey, S. A. Hashmi, *Journal of Power Sources* **2009**, 187, 627.
- [121] K. Matsumoto, T. Endo, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry* **2011**, 49, 3582.
- [122] K. Kimura, Y. Tominaga, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2017**, 164, A3357.
- [123] T. Blensdorf, A. Joenathan, M. Hunt, U. Werner-Zwanziger, B. D. Stein, W. E. Mahmoud, A. A. Al-Ghamdi, J. Carini, L. M. Bronstein, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2017**, 5, 3493.
- [124] A. Mejia, E. Benito, J. Guzman, L. Garrido, N. Garcia, M. Hoyos, P. Tiemblo, *Acs Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* **2016**, 4, 2114.
- [125] X. Zhan, J. Zhang, M. Liu, J. Lu, Q. Zhang, F. Chen, *ACS Applied Energy Materials* **2019**, 2, 1685.
- [126] Z. Xie, Z. Wu, X. An, A. Yoshida, Z. Wang, X. Hao, A. Abudula, G. Guan, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2019**, 586, 122.
- [127] J. E. Lim, M. S. Oh, J. H. Ahn, J. K. Kim, *Electrochimica Acta* **2017**, 238, 107.
- [128] S. T. C. L. Ndruru, D. Wahyuningrum, B. Bundjali, I. M. Arcana, *2019* **2019**, DOI: 10.9767/bcrec.14.2.3074.345-35713.
- [129] A. S. Hager, E. K. Arendt, *Food Hydrocolloids* **2013**, 32, 195.
- [130] M. Y. Chong, C. W. Liew, A. Numan, K. Yugal, K. Ramesh, H. Ng, T. V. Chong, S. Ramesh, *Ionics* **2016**, 22, 2421.
- [131] M. Y. Chong, A. Numan, C. W. Liew, H. M. Ng, K. Ramesh, S. Ramesh, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* **2018**, 117, 194.
- [132] T. Y. Yun, X. Li, S. H. Kim, H. C. Moon, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2018**, 10, 43993.
- [133] I. Osada, S. M. Hosseini, S. Jeong, S. Passerini, *ChemElectroChem* **2017**, 4, 463.
- [134] M. Wirey, M. Hunt, T. Blensdorf, B. D. Stein, U. Werner-Zwanziger, M. A. Hanson, W. E. Mahmoud, A. A. Al-Ghamdi, J. Carini, L. M. Bronstein, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, 217, 794.
- [135] C. Zhong, Y. D. Deng, W. B. Hu, J. L. Qiao, L. Zhang, J. J. Zhang, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2015**, 44, 7484.
- [136] B. S. Cho, J. Choi, K. Y. Kim, *Fiber. Polym.* **2017**, 18, 1452.
- [137] H. Q. Zhang, W. J. Wu, J. T. Wang, T. Zhang, B. B. Shi, J. D. Liu, S. K. Cao, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, 476, 136.
- [138] R. S. Malik, P. Verma, V. Choudhary, *Electrochimica Acta* **2015**, 152, 352.
- [139] X. Y. Wang, M. S. Jin, Y. X. Li, L. H. Zhao, *Electrochimica Acta* **2017**, 257, 290.
- [140] Y. Ma, L. B. Li, G. X. Gao, X. Y. Yang, J. You, P. X. Yang, *Colloid Surf. A-Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* **2016**, 502, 130.
- [141] J. Batalha, K. Dahmouche, R. B. Sampaio, A. D. Gomes, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2017**, 302, 11.
- [142] K. Yang, Z. Liao, Z. Zhang, L. Yang, S.-i. Hirano, *Materials Letters* **2019**, 236, 554.
- [143] T.-L. Chen, R. Sun, C. Willis, B. F. Morgan, F. L. Beyer, Y. A. Elabd, *Polymer* **2019**, 161, 128.
- [144] T. Huang, M.-C. Long, X.-L. Wang, G. Wu, Y.-Z. Wang, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2019**, 375, 122062.
- [145] A. Fdz De Anastro, N. Lago, C. Berlanga, M. Galcerán, M. Hilder, M. Forsyth, D. Mecerreyes, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2019**, 582, 435.
- [146] A. Le Mong, D. Kim, *Journal of Power Sources* **2019**, 422, 57.
- [147] H. Zhang, P. K. Shen, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2012**, 41, 2382.
- [148] S. S. Sekhon, P. Krishnan, B. Singh, K. Yamada, C. S. Kim, *Electrochimica Acta* **2006**, 52, 1639.
- [149] S. S. Sekhon, B. S. Lalia, J. S. Park, C. S. Kim, K. Yamada, *Journal of Materials Chemistry* **2006**, 16, 2256.
- [150] D. Wang, Y. F. Wang, H. T. Wan, J. L. Wang, L. L. Wang, *Rsc Advances* **2018**, 8, 10185.
- [151] Y. N. Chen, Z. M. Li, N. J. Chen, R. Li, Y. J. Zhang, K. Li, F. H. Wang, H. Zhu, *Electrochimica Acta* **2017**, 255, 335.
- [152] B. Lin, G. Qiao, F. Chu, S. Zhang, N. Yuan, J. Ding, *RSC Advances* **2017**, 7, 1056.
- [153] Y. Zhang, R. Xue, Y. Zhong, F. Jiang, M. Hu, Q. Yu, *Fuel Cells* **2018**, 18, 389.

- [154] Y. Li, Y. Shi, N. Mehio, M. S. Tan, Z. Y. Wang, X. H. Hu, G. Z. Chen, S. Dai, X. B. Jin, *Appl. Energy* **2016**, 175, 451.
- [155] C. Schmidt, T. Gluck, G. Schmidt-Naake, *Chemical Engineering & Technology* **2008**, 31, 13.
- [156] J. Maiti, N. Kakati, S. P. Woo, Y. S. Yoon, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **2018**, 155, 189.
- [157] M. K. Mistry, S. Subianto, N. R. Choudhury, N. K. Dutta, *Langmuir* **2009**, 25, 9240.
- [158] L. G. da Trindade, M. R. Becker, F. Celso, C. L. Petzhold, E. M. A. Martini, R. F. de Souza, *Polymer Engineering and Science* **2016**, 56, 1037.
- [159] L. G. da Trindade, E. C. Pereira, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2017**, DOI: 10.1002/ejic.2016015592369.
- [160] R. Sonnier, L. Dumazert, S. Livi, T. K. L. Nguyen, J. Duchet-Rumeau, H. Vahabi, P. Laheurte, *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* **2016**, 134, 186.
- [161] F. Xiao, K. Wu, F. B. Luo, Y. Y. Guo, S. H. Zhang, X. X. Du, Q. Q. Zhu, M. G. Lu, *Journal of Materials Science* **2017**, 52, 13992.
- [162] M. D. Aviles, N. Saurin, T. Espinosa, J. Sanes, J. Arias-Pardilla, F. J. Carrion, M. D. Bermudez, *Express Polym. Lett.* **2017**, 11, 219.
- [163] N. Saurin, J. Sanes, F. J. Carrion, M. D. Bermudez, *Rsc Advances* **2016**, 6, 37258.
- [164] N. Saurin, J. Sanes, M. D. Bermudez, *Tribology Letters* **2015**, 58.
- [165] X. Jia, Y. Yang, C. Wang, C. Zhao, R. Vijayaraghavan, D. R. MacFarlane, M. Forsyth, G. G. Wallace, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2014**, 6, 21110.
- [166] Y. Wang, S. Gong, S. J. Wang, G. P. Simon, W. Cheng, *Materials Horizons* **2016**, 3, 208.
- [167] Y. M. Kim, H. C. Moon, *Advanced Functional Materials* n/a, 1907290.
- [168] X. W. Ye, J. H. Guo, X. R. Zeng, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **2017**, 134, 8.
- [169] H. M. Yang, Y. K. Kwon, S. B. Lee, S. Kim, K. Hong, K. H. Lee, *Acs Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 8813.
- [170] H. Cheng, X. He, Z. Fan, J. Ouyang, *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**, 9.
- [171] S. Shin, Y. S. Park, S. Cho, I. You, I. S. Kang, H. C. Moon, U. Jeong, *Chemical Science* **2018**, 9, 2480.
- [172] Y. M. Kim, D. G. Seo, H. Oh, H. C. Moon, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2019**, 7, 161.
- [173] H. Hwang, S. Y. Park, J. K. Kim, Y. M. Kim, H. C. Moon, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2019**, 11, 4399.
- [174] M. Y. Teo, N. Kim, S. Kee, B. S. Kim, G. Kim, S. Hong, S. Jung, K. Lee, *Acs Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 819.
- [175] F. D. Krampa, Y. Aniweh, G. A. Awandare, P. Kanyong, *Sensors* **2017**, 17, 13.
- [176] V. A. Kusuma, M. K. Macala, J. Liu, A. M. Marti, R. J. Hirsch, L. J. Hill, D. Hopkinson, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2018**, 545, 292.
- [177] F. Ranjbaran, E. Kamio, H. Matsuyama, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2017**, 56, 12763.
- [178] X. Cai, T. Lei, D. Sun, L. Lin, *RSC Advances* **2017**, 7, 15382.
- [179] Y. Wang, T. Y. Goh, P. Goodrich, M. Atilhan, M. Khraisheh, D. Rooney, J. Thompson, J. Jacquemin, *Arabian Journal of Chemistry* **2017**, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2017.05.008>.
- [180] M. Fallanza, A. Ortiz, D. Gorri, I. Ortiz, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2013**, 444, 164.
- [181] L. Hu, J. Cheng, Y. Li, J. Liu, L. Zhang, J. Zhou, K. Cen, *Applied Surface Science* **2017**, 410, 249.
- [182] P. Nancarrow, L. Liang, Q. Gan, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, 472, 222.
- [183] K. Halder, M. M. Khan, J. Grnauer, S. Shishatskiy, C. Abetz, V. Filiz, V. Abetz, *Journal of Membrane Science* **2017**, 539, 368.
- [184] H. A. Mannan, D. F. Mohshim, H. Mukhtar, T. Murugesan, Z. Man, M. A. Bustam, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **2017**, 54, 98.
- [185] M. S. Mittenenthal, B. S. Flowers, J. E. Bara, J. W. Whitley, S. K. Spear, J. D. Roveda, D. A. Wallace, M. S. Shannon, R. Honee, R. Martens, D. T. Daly, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2017**, 56, 5055.
- [186] R. Mejri, J. C. Dias, S. B. Hentati, M. S. Martins, C. M. Costa, S. Lanceros-Mendez, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2016**, 453, 8.
- [187] M. D. Bennett, D. J. Leo, *Sens. Actuator A-Phys.* **2004**, 115, 79.
- [188] M. D. Bennett, D. J. Leo, G. L. Wilkes, F. L. Beyer, T. W. Pechar, *Polymer* **2006**, 47, 6782.

- [189] M. Li, X. Zhang, S. Zeng, L. bai, H. Gao, J. Deng, Q. Yang, S. Zhang, *RSC Advances* **2017**, 7, 6422.
- [190] W. Lu, K. Henry, C. Turchi, J. Pellegrino, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2008**, 155, A361.
- [191] G. P. Pandey, S. A. Hashmi, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2013**, 1, 3372.
- [192] A. M. Obeidat, M. A. Gharaibeh, M. Obaidat, *Journal of Energy Storage* **2017**, 13, 123.
- [193] S. K. Singh, Shalu, L. Balo, H. Gupta, V. K. Singh, A. K. Tripathi, Y. L. Verma, R. K. Singh, *Energy* **2018**, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.024>.
- [194] W. Zhai, Y. W. Zhang, L. Wang, F. Cai, X. M. Liu, Y. J. Shi, H. Yang, *Solid State Ion.* **2016**, 286, 111.
- [195] H. P. S. Missan, B. S. Lalia, K. Karan, A. Maxwell, *Materials Science and Engineering B-Advanced Functional Solid-State Materials* **2010**, 175, 143.
- [196] A. Fericola, S. Panero, B. Scrosati, M. Tamada, H. Ohno, *Chemphyschem* **2007**, 8, 1103.
- [197] C. Croitoru, A. M. Varodi, M. C. Timar, I. C. Roata, E. M. Stanciu, A. Pascu, *Journal of Materials Science* **2018**, 53, 4132.
- [198] Q. M. Tu, L. Q. Fan, F. Pan, J. L. Huang, Y. Gu, J. M. Lin, M. L. Huang, Y. F. Huang, J. H. Wu, *Electrochimica Acta* **2018**, 268, 562.
- [199] P. Cao, Y. X. Fan, J. R. Yu, R. M. Wang, P. F. Song, Y. B. Xiong, *New J. Chem.* **2018**, 42, 3909.
- [200] Y. X. Li, M. S. Zhang, X. Y. Wang, Z. Li, L. H. Zhao, *Electrochimica Acta* **2016**, 222, 1308.
- [201] W. J. Wu, J. T. Wang, J. D. Liu, P. P. Chen, H. Q. Zhang, J. J. Huang, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **2017**, 42, 11400.
- [202] R. S. Malik, S. N. Tripathi, D. Gupta, V. Choudhary, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **2014**, 39, 12826.
- [203] Q. Che, B. Sun, R. He, *Electrochimica Acta* **2008**, 53, 4428.
- [204] Q. T. Che, L. Zhou, J. L. Wang, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* **2015**, 206, 10.
- [205] D.-J. You, Z. Yin, Y.-k. Ahn, S. Cho, H. Kim, D. Shin, J. Yoo, Y. S. Kim, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **2017**, 52, 1.
- [206] H. Huo, N. Zhao, J. Sun, F. Du, Y. Li, X. Guo, *Journal of Power Sources* **2017**, 372, 1.
- [207] K. H. S. Iessa, Y. Zhang, G. A. Zhang, F. Xiao, S. Wang, *Journal of Power Sources* **2016**, 302, 92.
- [208] L. Mao, Y. Li, C. Y. Chi, H. S. O. Chan, J. S. Wu, *Nano Energy* **2014**, 6, 119.
- [209] C. W. Liew, K. H. Arifin, J. Kawamura, Y. Iwai, S. Ramesh, A. K. Arof, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* **2017**, 458, 97.
- [210] C. W. Liew, S. Ramesh, A. K. Arof, *Energy* **2016**, 109, 546.
- [211] P. Tamilarasan, S. Ramaprabhu, *Energy* **2013**, 51, 374.
- [212] P. F. R. Ortega, J. P. C. Trigueiro, G. G. Silva, R. L. Lavall, *Electrochimica Acta* **2016**, 188, 809.
- [213] G. P. Pandey, Y. Kumar, S. A. Hashmi, *Solid State Ion.* **2011**, 190, 93.
- [214] L. Xie, Y. Qin, H.-Y. Chen, *Sensors and Actuators B-Chemical* **2013**, 186, 321.
- [215] H. Okuzaki, S. Takagi, F. Hishiki, R. Tanigawa, *Sensors and Actuators B-Chemical* **2014**, 194, 59.
- [216] K. Hooshyari, M. Javanbakht, M. Adibi, *Electrochimica Acta* **2016**, 205, 142.
- [217] S. Y. Chew, J. Z. Sun, J. Z. Wang, H. K. Liu, M. Forsyth, D. R. MacFarlane, *Electrochimica Acta* **2008**, 53, 6460.
- [218] S. Thayumanasundaram, V. S. Rangasamy, J. W. Seo, J. P. Locquet, *Electrochimica Acta* **2017**, 240, 371.
- [219] M. Doyle, S. K. Choi, G. Proulx, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2000**, 147, 34.
- [220] A. Noda, M. Watanabe, *Electrochimica Acta* **2000**, 45, 1265.
- [221] P. Snedden, A. I. Cooper, K. Scott, N. Winterton, *Macromolecules* **2003**, 36, 4549.
- [222] K. Lunstroot, K. Driesen, P. Nockemann, L. Viau, P. H. Mutin, A. Vioux, K. Binnemans, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2010**, 12, 1879.
- [223] M. A. Klingshirn, S. K. Spear, R. Subramanian, J. D. Holbrey, J. G. Huddleston, R. D. Rogers, *Chemistry of Materials* **2004**, 16, 3091.
- [224] G. Chen, N. Chen, Q. Wang, *Materials & Design* **2018**, 157, 273.
- [225] L. Zhao, Y. Li, Z. Liu, H. Shimizu, *Chemistry of Materials* **2010**, 22, 5949.
- [226] G. B. Thorat, S. Gupta, Z. V. P. Murthy, *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering* **2017**, 25, 1402.

Appendix

Acronym	Chemical name
[AMIM][Cl]	1-allyl-3-methyl imidazolium chloride
[EMIM][TFSI]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide
[EMIM][C ₂ SO ₄]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium ethylsulfate
[EMIM][BF ₄]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate
[EMIM][DCA]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide
[EMIM][Tfo]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[EMIM][TFSI]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide
[EMIM][TCB]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetracyanoborate
[EMIM][CF ₃ SO ₃]	1-ethyl-3-methyl imidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[EMIM][Cl]	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
[EIM][Tfo]	1-ethylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[Cmim][Cl]	1-carboxybutyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
[BMIM][PF ₆]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorofostate
[BMIM][BF ₄]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate
[BMIM][I]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium iodide
[BMIM][Cl]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
[BMIM][Tfo]	1-butyl-3-methyl-imidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[BMIM][TFSI]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide
[BMMIM][BF ₄]	1-butyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate
[BMIM][BTI]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide
[BMIM][CF ₃ SO ₃]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[BMIM][I]	1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium iodide
[BVIM][Br]	1-butyl-3-vinyl imidazolium bromide
[BMPyr][TFSI]	1-butyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethyl sulfonyl imide
[BACO][EA]	2-butylamino carbonyl]oxy]ethyl acrylate
[HMIM][Cl]	1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
[HMIM][TFSI]	1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide
[HPy][PF ₆]	1-hexylpyridinium hexafluorophosphate
[C ₈ MIM] ₃ [La(NO ₃) ₆]	1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium hexanitratolanthanate
[C ₈ MIM] ₂ [Eu(NO ₃) ₅]	1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium pentanitratoeuropate

[C ₃ OHMIM][BF ₄]	1-(3-hydroxypropyl)-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroboride
[C ₁₀ MI][CF ₃ SO ₃]	1-decyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate
[C ₁₂ MIM][Br]	1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide
[C ₁₆ MIM][Cl]	1-hexadecyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride
[DMBuIm][H ₂ PO ₄]	2,3 dimethyl-1-butyl imidazolium dihydrogen phosphate
[DEMA][Tfo]	Diethylmethylammonium trifluoromethane-sulfonate
[DEMA][TfOH]	Diethylmethylamine triflate
[DEMM][TFSI]	N,N-diethyl-N-(2-methacryloylethyl)-N-methylammonium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide
[DMOIm][TFSI]	2,3-dimethyl-1-octylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonylimide
[EOHMIM][Gly]	1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-3-methyl imidazolium glycinate
[Li][TFSI]	lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide
[N _{1 1 1 2OH}][TFSI]	N,N,N-trimethyl-N-(2-hydroxyethyl) ammonium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide
[PMMI][TFSI]	1-propyl-2,3-dimethylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide
[PMIM][TFSI]	3-methyl-1-propylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide
[P13][TFSI]	1-methyl-3-propylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide
[PP13][TFSI]	1-methyl-3-propylpiperidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide
[Pyr14][TFSI]	N-n-butyl-N-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide
PP14 [TFSI]	(N-methyl-N-butyl-piperidine-bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide
[TMA][OH]	tetramethylammonium hydroxyde
[VBIIm][NTf ₂]	1-vinyl-3-butylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)-imide
[VCMIM][Cl]	1-vinyl-3-carboxymethylimidazolium chloride
[SBVIM][HSO ₄]	1-(4-sulfonic acid)butyl-3-vinylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate
[4MBP][BF ₄]	1-butyl-4-methylpyridinium tetrafluoroborate
[Nbmd][OH]	<i>“gemini-type basic morpholine ionic liquid”</i>
[MTO][Im]	methyltrioctylammonium bis (trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide
TTDPP	trihexyltetradecylphosphonium bis (2,4,4-trimethylpentyl) phosphinate

Biographies

Daniela Correia graduated in Chemistry in 2009, obtained her master degree in Characterization Techniques and Chemical Analysis in 2011 and the PhD degree in Materials Engineering in 2016, all from the University of Minho, Portugal. After obtaining her PhD degree, she obtained a fellowship focusing on the development of electroactive materials with different morphologies and dimensionalities for novel tissue engineering approaches and in the surface modification adhesion and wetting properties of the materials. Currently, she is a Post-Doc researcher at Physics center in the University of Minho and at Chemistry center in the University of Trás-os-Montes, Vila Real, Portugal. Her work is devoted to the development of a new generation of active materials comprising different morphologies and dimensionalities based on electroactive polymers and composites comprising electroactive polymers and ionic liquids, among others, for biomedical and sensors and actuators applications.

Javier Reguera is an Ikerbasque Research Fellow at BCMaterials Basque Center for Materials, Applications, and Nanostructures, Leioa, Spain. He received a bachelor's degree in Physics and a PhD in Materials Science (2008) at the University of Valladolid (Spain). He was a Fulbright

fellow at Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA) 2009–2011, a postdoctoral scientist at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland) 2011–2014, and a research associate at CIC BiomaGUNE (Spain) 2014-2019. He joined BCMaterials in 2019 where his research interest includes the synthesis of smart and multicomponent nanomaterials, self-assembly, multifunctional nanocomposites, and applications in nanobiomedicine, imaging and sensing.

S. Lanceros-Mendez is Ikerbasque Professor at the BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures, Leioa, Spain, where he is the Scientific Director. He is Associate Professor at the Physics Department of the University of Minho, Portugal (on leave), where also belongs to the Center of Physics. From 2012 to 2014 he was also Associate Researcher at the INL – International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory. He graduated in physics at the University of the Basque Country, Leioa, Spain and obtained his Ph.D. degree at the Institute of Physics of the Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, Germany. He was Research Scholar at Montana State University, Bozeman, MT, USA and visiting scientist at the Pennsylvania State University, USA and University of Potsdam, Germany, among others. His work is focused in the area of smart and multifunctional materials for sensors and actuators, energy and biomedical applications.

Based on their interesting properties, ionic liquids (ILs) have been used for the development of polymer-based multifunctional materials. The suitable combination of both IL and polymer properties allows developing advanced materials with tailored functional responses and applicability in areas including sensors and actuators, environment (air and water remediation), energy generation and storage, and biomedicine.

Keyword Ionic liquid - polymer multifunctional composites

D.M. Correia^{1,2}, L.C. Fernandes^{2,3}, P.M. Martins^{2,4}, C. García-Astrain³, C.M. Costa^{2,5}, J. Reguera^{3, 6}, S. Lancers-Méndez^{3,6*}*

Ionic liquids-polymer composites: a new smart platform for multifunctional applications

ToC figure

